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CODECO

Cognitive Decentralised
Edge Cloud Orchestration

D25: CODECO Ecosystem Community-building Report v2.0

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Executive Summary

The CODECO Deliverable D25 - CODECO Ecosystem Community-building Report version 2 corresponds to the updated version of D24 - CODECO Ecosystem Community-building Report version 1 [1], and it refers to the work under development in Work Package (WP) 7 and Task T7.1 - Toolkits Exploitation and Open-source Community-building. This deliverable describes the open-source and community-building strategy of CODECO and shows the results achieved so far, with special focus on the second year of the project. The aim of this strategy is to best prepare CODECO's open-source results for (i) exploitation, sustainability, and adoption, and (ii) building a community of developers and early adopters.

While D24 was focused on the open-source strategy and the first community-building actions to raise awareness on the CODECO project, addressing the specific challenges of open source in collaborative research projects, D25 brings the attention to the CODECO Basic Open-Source Toolkit, stable and consolidated version released in June 2024, and the actions done during this last year to gather a developer community around it.

In terms of Intellectual Property (IP) and License Management, the basic agreement for CODECO open source was that it would be licensed under a permissive or weak copyleft license, including, by default, Apache-2.0, MIT, BSD-3-Clause, and EPL-2.0. As a further step, the CODECO component leaders agreed to license their code under the Apache-2.0 license, enabling the use of the IP semi-automatic Tools to assess license compliance, the solution of potential license incompatibility issues and the implementation of open-source best practices.

Keywords: Collaboration, Communication, Community, Community building, Copyright, Developer, Development, Dissemination, Header, Intellectual Property, License, Open source, Promotion, Repository, Software, Sustainability, Toolkit.

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Disclaimer

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Table of Contents

Executive Summary	3
1 Introduction	10
1.1 Document Scope	10
1.2 Dependencies.....	10
1.3 Document Structure.....	11
2 Open-source and Community-building	12
2.1 Challenges of Open source in Research Projects.....	12
2.2 Open-source and Community-building Strategy.....	13
2.2.1 Landscaping	13
2.2.2 Open Collaboration Environment	14
2.2.3 Open-source Licenses and IP Management	14
2.2.4 OSS Community-building.....	15
3 CODECO OSS Assets	17
3.1 The CODECO OSS Basic Toolkit	17
3.1.1 ACM: Automated Configuration Management	18
3.1.2 PDLC: Privacy-preserving Decentralized Learning and Context-awareness	18
3.1.3 NetMA: Network Management and Adaptation	19
3.1.4 MDM: Metadata Management.....	19
3.1.5 SWM: Scheduling and Workload Migration	20
3.2 CODEF.....	21
3.3 Data Generator.....	21
3.4 Use-Cases Apps.....	22
3.4.1 P1 Smart Monitoring of the Public Infrastructure	22
3.4.2 P2 Vehicular Digital Twin for Safe Urban Mobility	23
3.4.3 P3 MDS across Decentralised Edge-Cloud.....	24
3.4.4 P4 Demand-side Management in Decentralized Grids.....	24
3.4.5 P5 Decentralised Wireless AGV Control Manufacturing	25
3.4.6 P6 Automated Crownstone Application Deployment for Smart Buildings	26
4 Implementing Open Collaboration Best Practices	28
4.1 Open Collaboration – Eclipse Research Labs.....	28
4.1.1 Research Labs.....	28
4.1.2 Development Process.....	31
4.2 Copyright Headers and Repository Best Practices	34
4.2.1 Copyright Headers	34
4.2.2 Repository Best Practices Implementation.....	34
4.3 OSS Licenses and IP Validation	37
4.3.1 OSS Licenses in CODECO.....	37
4.3.2 IP Validation.....	41
4.4 Trainings.....	43
5 OSS Community-building Year 2	45
5.1 Target Communities	46
5.2 Community-building Activities and Impact.....	47

5.3	Media Dissemination and Press Releases.....	50
5.3.1	OSS Oriented Events.....	50
5.3.2	Engagement in OSS Communities.....	53
6	OSS Community-building Planned Activities	56
7	Summary and Next Steps	59
8	Appendix 1 – OSS Community-building Year 1	60
9	References	65

List of Figures

Figure 1. The OSS license spectrum.....	15
Figure 2. High-level illustration of the CODECO framework and its main components.	17
Figure 3. The CODECO Research Labs GitLab.....	29
Figure 4. The Experimentation Framework and Demonstrations sub-group.	30
Figure 5. Use-Cases sub-group.	30
Figure 6. Pipelines in GitLab Runners corresponding to the CODECO project.....	31
Figure 7. Most recent issues currently open in CODECO Research Labs.	32
Figure 8. Current status of the issue board in CODECO Research Labs.....	33
Figure 9. Copyright header in the CODECO OSS code.	34
Figure 10. All the CODECO components and sub-components licensed under Apache-2.0. .	40
Figure 11. Snapshot of the report analysing the dependencies in the CODECO code.	42
Figure 12. Issues in the CODECO Research Labs corresponding to IP dependencies.	43
Figure 13. CODECO at Embedded World 2024, in Nuremberg.....	51
Figure 14. Red Hat team presenting CODECO at Tech talk, Ireland.	52
Figure 15. CODECO present at OCX 2024.	53
Figure 16. First CODECO inception workshop, collocated with HIPEAC 2024 conference.....	55
Figure 17. Main OSS community-building activities foreseen from M12 until M36.....	57
Figure 18. CODECO article in Eclipse Newsletter in July 2023.	62
Figure 19. CODECO poster and CODECO team during EclipseCon 2023.....	63
Figure 20. First EUCloudEdgeloT concertation meeting.....	64

List of Tables

Table 1. CODECO repositories visibility, license used and presence of Readme file.	35
Table 2. Copyright owners for the CODECO repositories and % of files including a header...	36
Table 3. Training on open-source best practices provided to CODECO consortium in 2023. .	43
Table 4. Open-source community-building activities held until M24.....	48
Table 5. Initial OSS community-building activities foreseen for the third year of CODECO.....	57
Table 6. Open-source community-building activities held until M12.....	60

List of Acronyms and Definitions

Acronym	Meaning
ACM	Automated Configuration Management
AGPL	Affero General Public License
AGV	Automated Guided Vehicle
AI	Artificial intelligence
AIOTI	Alliance for IoT and Edge Computing Innovation
API	Application Programming Interface
AR	Academia and Research
BSD	Berkeley Software Distribution
CA	Consortium Agreement
CC	Creative Commons
CI/CD	Continuous Integration and Continuous Development
CODECO	Cognitive, Decentralized Edge-Cloud Orchestration
CODEF	CODECO Experimental Framework
CR	Custom Resource
CRDs	Custom-Defined Resources
DEV	Developers
DL	Decentralized Learning
DT	Digital Twin
EC	European commission
ECA	Eclipse Contributor Agreement
EMO	Eclipse Management Organization
EPL	Eclipse Public License
EU	European Union
EUs	End-Users
Pub	Public in General
GA	Grant Agreement
GOV	Government, municipalities, public authorities, and policymakers
HE	Horizon Europe
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IETF	Internet Engineering Task Force
IoT	Internet of Things
IP	Intellectual Property
IRCEP	Innovation and Research Community Engagement Programme
K8s	Kubernetes
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MIT	Massachusetts Institute of Technology
MDM	Metadata Management
ML	Machine Learning
Mx	Month x of the CODECO project
NetMA	Network Management and Adaptation

OCM	Open Cluster Management
OCX	Open Community Experience
OS	Open source
OSS	Open-source Software
PDLC	Privacy-preserving Decentralized Learning and Context-awareness
PV	Photovoltaic
QoE	Quality of Experience
SDO	Standardization entities and open-source communities
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprise
SWM	Scheduling and Workload Migration
TF	Task Force
USB	Universal Serial Bus
V2X	Vehicle-to-everything
VRU	Vulnerable Road User
WG	Working Group
Yx	Year x of the CODECO project

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1 Introduction

This deliverable presents the CODECO open-source and community-building strategy that is being implemented during the course of the project.

CODECO is committed to deliver its project results as professional, sustainable, and usable open-source software and to implement measures to build a community around these open-source results. Therefore, this deliverable describes the efforts made towards these goals in the context of WP7, task T7.1 (based on the technical work done in WP2 and WP3) from M13 to M24. While the first year was the initial definition and awareness phase, during the following twelve months the project has reached the maturity phase and a stable and consolidated version of the CODECO Open-Source Toolkit has been released, the open-source best practices have been implemented and the communication activities to engage with CODECO stakeholders and its open-source ambitions in the relevant communities have been carried out.

1.1 Document Scope

This deliverable is the second in a series of three, covering the work of *Task 7.1 - Toolkits Exploitation and Open-source Community-building*, from M13 (January 2024) to M24 (December 2024). Thus, it shows the strategy which was introduced in the Deliverable D24 [1] and is now being implemented, along with the activities conducted during this period. The last update of this report will be provided in M36 (December 2025), at the end of the project.

Naturally, the work of T7.1 happens in close collaboration to all tasks dealing with dissemination, communication, exploitation, and ecosystem building. From the high-level perspective, these activities contribute to CODECO **Objective O5: To build a consolidated ecosystem, appealing to the different CODECO stakeholder groups.**¹

1.2 Dependencies

In terms of defining the CODECO Open-source Toolkit, this deliverable is heavily dependent on the work done in WP2, mainly Task 2.2, T2.3, and T2.4 as these tasks laid the foundation for the CODECO architecture and the envisioned open-source ecosystem, as described in the CODECO deliverable *D10 - Technological Guidelines, Reference Architecture, and Initial Open-source Ecosystem Design v2.0* [3]. The second strong dependency is to WP3, namely Task 3.6, in which the actual integrated CODECO Open-source Toolkit was developed and reported in *D12 - CODECO Basic Operation and Open Toolkit v2.0* [5]. The last dependency corresponds to the work done under WP4, during the second stage of development of CODECO, T4.4, supporting tasks and extensions to the CODECO components to manage automation across federated clusters.

In terms of community-building, this deliverable is strongly related to all other tasks of WP7 which rely on a well-defined, professional CODECO Open-source Toolkit for exploitation and ecosystem development. Furthermore, it depends on WP6 because alignment is needed with the overall CODECO dissemination and communication strategy (*D21 - Dissemination, Communication, Promotion Plan* [6]).

¹ With a strong focus on developers.

1.3 Document Structure

The deliverable is structured as follows:

- Section 2 introduces the open-source and community-building strategy for CODECO taking into consideration the peculiarities of research projects when making it open source.
- Section 0 presents the CODECO Open-source Toolkit.
- Section 0 describes how open-source best practices are implemented to maximize the chances of creating successful open-source.
- Section 0 reports on the community-building activities performed during M13 – M24.
- Section 6 presents the initial plan concerning Open-Source Software (OSS) community-building activities for year 3 of CODECO.
- Section 0 concludes the report corresponding to this second year.
- Section 8 is the placeholder for the community building activities developed for CODECO during year 1, the previous reporting period.

2 Open-source and Community-building

The definition of open source implies that the source code is distributed under a license in which the copyright holders grant others the power to run, access, modify and re-distribute the software to anyone and for any purpose [7] [8], thus enabling the development to happen under an open, collaborative model. Throughout the years, the OSS development model has become increasingly popular around the world. Today, open-source components are the core building blocks of application software in most innovative domains, providing developers with an ever-growing selection of off-the-shelf possibilities that they can use for assembling their products faster and more efficiently [9].

Open source allows code to be used (freely), studied (in full transparency), improved and shared (collaboratively). To achieve this, there are open-source licences that comply with the open-source definition and allow the software to be freely used, modified, and shared.

Because open source is all about collaboration, the concept of communities is of major importance. Generally speaking, *“a community is a group of people united by a common identity and collective purpose who engage in activities together over time. Communities develop unique sets of shared values, principles, and norms that distinguish them from others and provide members with a sense of belonging. An open-source software community is a group of people united by the shared purpose of developing, maintaining, extending, and promoting a specific body of open-source software. These communities are often globally distributed—their members occupy different geographic regions and work across numerous industries. What unites them is their common vision for the open-source software project—as well as the spirit of camaraderie and collective identity that participating in the community affords them.”* [10].

2.1 Challenges of Open source in Research Projects

According to a study by Ait et al. [11] *“a considerable number of projects [on GitHub] die in the first year of existence with the survival rate decreasing year after year. In fact, the probability of surviving longer than five years is less than 50%, though some types of projects have better chances of survival.”* While this study does not specifically address open-source results of research projects, the survival rate of code on GitHub resulting from research projects is not much higher than what was found in this study.

Looking at the software industry, open source is ubiquitous and has become an integral part of leading companies' business strategies and products, as corroborated by several examples [12], [13], [14], [15] and best practices [16], [17]. However, introducing an open-source strategy in a company is still not an easy task and can be a lengthy process; but once the decision is taken, measures can be implemented, the management can set structures and processes, etc.

Instead, a research project is not owned by a single entity, but consists of many different actors from industry, applied research and academia who agree to work towards a common goal (or set of goals) for a limited period of time. In terms of open source, the aim is to avoid the situation described by Ait et al, i.e., to avoid creating *“abandonware”* that is publicly available but has little chance of surviving beyond the three years of the research project. The nature of a research

project as a collaborative endeavour for a limited period of time adds some complexity to achieving this goal.

Different organizations from different industries, domains and backgrounds come together with diverse ideas, beliefs, and experience regarding open source. While some partners may have adopted open source in their organization, this may not be the case for others. This becomes even more important when thinking about background and foreground of the research project. While some partners may bring open-source background into the project others may bring proprietary software. This has an impact on the envisioned open-source foreground to be developed during the project and poses challenges in defining which parts of the project should be released as open source and to what extent. However, if these challenges are properly addressed, the unique setup of a research project can be used to produce results in open source that have an impact: results that are not thrown away after a three-year project; results that are built upon, reused, extended, continued and developed after the project is over; results that have a longer-term impact on research and innovation agendas; results that can lead to new business models, start-ups and growth.

Not all these achievements can be realized in the scope of a three-years research project. But the key point is to turn the described challenges into advantages and **create a strong basis that increases the chances of reaching these goals in the long run**. To do so, a realistic yet ambitious open-source and community-building strategy has to be implemented.

2.2 Open-source and Community-building Strategy

A good open-source and community-building strategy should (i) draw and keep track of the open-source landscape of the project, (ii) create an environment that allows for open collaboration right from the start, (iii) implement sufficient Intellectual Property (IP) management and (iv) lay out measures for community-building.

2.2.1 Landscaping

The open-source landscape should set the boundaries and scope of the project's open-source ambitions. It tracks partners' background and defines the output that should be released. It also identifies the existing communities associated to certain background and potential new ones. Landscaping is an ongoing activity starting from the proposal when the initial concept is drafted, continuously answering to these questions: Will the project develop new tools or products? Does it aim to provide a full-fledged integrated platform? Does it aim to extend or contribute significantly to already existing tools that partners bring into the project? Or a combination of all of those?

It is important to identify and state as clearly as possible which parts of the project results will be open-source and in what form, answering the aforementioned questions. This will contribute to a coherent open-source landscape for the whole project.

Section 0 provides this overview of the CODECO Open-source Toolkit.

2.2.2 Open Collaboration Environment

As the name suggests, open-source development is meant to be done in the open. In most cases, it is not a good idea to wait until the end of the project to release code, because "*the code needs polishing before it can be shown to the public*", or "*it's not ready*", for whatever reason. Developing behind closed doors is an open-source antipathy. It will slow the project down, and the effort to "*do it later*" will continue to grow. It will cause a lot of pain.

Infrastructure (i.e., a public repo) should be set up at the start of the project, and open-source best practices should be implemented from the start. This will allow everyone to become familiar with open-source development and will encourage knowledge transfer. It is a prerequisite for reaping all the benefits of open collaboration - something that should be a pillar of any research project.

Section 0 describes the implementation of the open collaboration environment and best practices for doing proper open source.

2.2.3 Open-source Licenses and IP Management

As already mentioned, it is important to discuss open-source licences. The consortium should agree on (the types of) licences for the project results. For example, to allow commercial use of the open-source results, strong copyleft licences should not be brought into the project (at least not without prior agreement).

Moreover, as the project runs and code is developed, it is wise to keep track of all incoming IP and licenses. The aim is to identify problems as early as possible. For example, replacing a license-incompatible library will be much easier if it is caught early, rather than later, when a lot of code already depends on it. Typically, IP and licensing are not straightforward issues and require a certain amount of training, coordination and, ideally, tool support.

Figure 1 shows the license spectrum, ordered from strong copyright (or proprietary licenses, on the right) to permissive licenses (on the left), until the *Public domain*, which corresponds to an unlicensed piece of software.

Section 0 describes how IP and license management are implemented for CODECO.

Figure 1. The OSS license spectrum.

2.2.4 OSS Community-building

When an initial open-source landscape is drawn, relevant communities can be identified. Of course, these communities are defined by open-source projects that partners bring into the project, but it is always worth thinking about other communities beyond the obvious ones. The old principle “*don’t reinvent the wheel*” also applies for community-building: Building up a new community from scratch is a long-term, time- and cost-consuming process. As with software, a lot of open-source communities exist and tapping into those is much more promising than trying to produce the next important thing, especially in the scope of a research project. Whether trying to build a new community or interacting with existing ones, we will follow the “**FREE** your community” philosophy for successful open-source community-building:

- **Feed** your community: In order to create and maintain a strong and sustainable relationship with a growing community, it is essential to provide it with regular information on the progress of the project while documenting the different facets of the project. At the same time, these actions allow us to build a knowledge base on the project that is accessible to all those who want to learn more.
- **Respect** your community: As soon as some code is available, it is important to share it with our communities. Even if we are not yet sure of its quality, giving access to our code to people outside the project increases our chances of getting feedback from our early adopters. “Every bug report is a love letter,” says Erich Gamma. This is absolutely true. In order to get that reaction, our early adopters will have to be able to (a) find our code, (b) download it, (c) install it, (d) test it. And, finally, whoever encounters a problem, will then have to decide to (e) contact us to report a bug, submit a request for enhancement or a simple question. This feedback becomes a real demonstration of their interest in our work, and we should not disappoint them.
- **Embrace** your community: The communities are not waiting for us. We may have an innovative idea, but if we do not know how to present it to these communities, if we cannot show them that we understand their needs and know how to meet them, we will miss the opportunity to attract them. That is why understanding them is essential. And

the best way to achieve this level of understanding is to attend conferences, organize or participate in local events, interact with existing user groups and, last but not least, meet communities you are not used to meeting.

- **Engage** your community: At some point, it is necessary to engage our communities. Remote webinars, workshops, contests, or hackathons are great ways to engage them. These bring useful feedback in terms of how the project is understood, how the platform is used, etc.

Section 0 reports on the initial activities towards open-source community-building for CODECO.

3 CODECO OSS Assets

3.1 The CODECO OSS Basic Toolkit

CODECO is a software-based orchestration framework, interoperable with K8s, that aims to support a next generation of container orchestrators that can adapt, learn, and develop appropriate response and adaptation. The CODECO Open-Source Toolkit describes the collection of open-source components that can be used. This toolkit includes all components that deliver the CODECO platform as fully functional, exploitable open-source software: Automated Configuration Management (ACM), Privacy-preserving Decentralized Learning and Context-awareness (PDLC), Network Management and Adaptation (NetMA), Metadata Management (MDM), Scheduling and Workload Migration (SWM) (see *D12 - CODECO Basic Operation and Open Toolkit v2.0* [5]).

The aim of this section is to provide an overview of these components from an open-source perspective. This includes a brief description of each component, its value proposition to developers, and the current state and plans for open sourcing.

Figure 2 provides a high-level representation of the CODECO components.

Figure 2. High-level illustration of the CODECO framework and its main components.

Detailed in-depth specifications of each component can be found in the CODECO deliverable *D12 - CODECO Basic Operation and Open Toolkit v2.0* [5] and the elaboration of the architectural design is provided in *D10 - Technological Guidelines, Reference Architecture, and Initial Open-source Ecosystem Design v2.0* [3].

The next sections provide an overview of each CODECO component and the license under which they are licensed.

3.1.1 ACM: Automated Configuration Management

Summary

ACM provides methodologies and tools that support automatic configuration regarding application setup and deployment across Edge-Cloud, for single and multi-cluster environments. Aiming to provide concrete setup, configuration, and synchronization mechanisms suitable for federated cluster environments, CODECO integrates ACM, which offers automated management mechanisms to support both cluster configuration and application deployment setup, runtime workflows, and resource management (i.e., considering also non-k8s environments), and, at the same time, to assure minimum human intervention.

Value Proposition

ACM will add support for multi-clustering and resource management at the Edge, efficiently, and cover novel Cloud-to-Edge use cases, explicitly.

Open Sourcing

ACM is based on the *Open Cluster Management (OCM)*² community driven project which is the upstream project for Red Hat Advanced Cluster Management. ACM will be licensed under Apache-2.0.

3.1.2 PDLC: Privacy-preserving Decentralized Learning and Context-awareness

Summary

PDLC is the heart of the CODECO cognitive orchestration. It is used to provide a finer-grained orchestration, by developing estimations about the system stability, and providing those estimations to other components such as SWM (for the purpose of re-scheduling) and NetMA (for the purpose of network reservations). PDLC has a key role during the application run-time. Based on specific target performance profiles (e.g., resilience, greenness) provided by user DEV during the application deployment setup, PDLC i) generates combined target performance node weights based on data-compute-network; ii) generates node weight estimates based on the combined values, and resource status from cluster infrastructures. It uses this information to train decentralized learning models that aim to provide forecasting and predictions about future behaviour of the infrastructure nodes and deployed applications. The output of PDLC is provided in the form of Kubernetes *Custom-Defined Resources (CRDs)* which can then be exploited by other CODECO components, such as SWM and NetMA, to make more intelligent and insightful decisions in terms of scheduling, workload migration and resource management.

Value Proposition

Further the intelligence of cloud-edge orchestration frameworks based on cross-layer context data and decentralized intelligence that generate exploitable insights and predictions.

² <https://open-cluster-management.io/>

Open Sourcing

All developments and sub-components of PDLC are being provided as OSS. Community engagement with the component is crucial to receive feedback about the provided context information and prediction models and adapt them to best suit the needs of the community end-users. The current version of available PDLC sub-components are licensed under Apache 2.0.

3.1.3 NetMA: Network Management and Adaptation

Summary

NetMA is an advanced solution for managing and adapting networks, with the primary goal of simplifying the configuration of interconnections and enhancing the flexibility of Edge-Cloud operations. It effectively addresses the integration of internetworking control to support a wide range of network environments, including fixed, wireless, and cellular networks that will be the basis for a mobile and heterogeneous Edge-Cloud continuum, which will have to be supported by CODECO.

Within CODECO, NetMA plays a pivotal role in handling critical aspects such as software-defined networking capabilities, secure data exchange, predictive behaviour, and integrated network functionality exposure through standardized methods and K8s APIs.

Value Proposition

NetMA provides an improvement on the multi-domain connectivity, abstracting the local and physical location of the worker nodes by deploying an easy-to-use overlay connectivity mechanism. It also maintains a complete and updated view of the current state of the network, both underlay and overlay, enhancing the network knowledge that the network manager normally relies on (being such view of the network state exposed and then consumed by other CODECO components).

Open Sourcing

NetMA is licensed as open-source under Apache-2.0 license. This license allows keeping the rights of the module but at the same time allows other potential partners to help with the maintenance and improvement of the module.

3.1.4 MDM: Metadata Management

Summary

MDM provides a common place where all metadata from systems, applications and data can be brought together on a graph. This enables sophisticated analytics to gain insights into the behaviour of complex systems, and to take action to report or correct that system behaviour. In CODECO, MDM provides an API that can be used to calculate parameters about a multi-cluster Kubernetes system to drive intelligent application scheduling algorithms. Examples of these parameters include how 'green' the energy used for computation is, how well workloads and systems comply with predefined rules, and so on.

Metadata is provided using a JSON schema-based model that describes entities with properties and relationships between them. This metadata is provided by connectors that specialise in collecting metadata from specific systems and applications. These include Kubernetes clusters themselves, but can be enriched with metadata about any system, provided a connector is developed for it.

The metadata model can be fully customised to the needs of a particular use case, although reuse is encouraged to facilitate the extensibility of existing applications and analysis logic.

Value Proposition

Enable mechanisms to assess how complex systems in the cloud-to-edge continuum behave by performing queries on the metadata graph. The results of the assessment can be used to drive system configuration and actuation, for example to decide where to schedule pods across different Kubernetes clusters. Those results may also be compared with requirements from policies defined by the end-user of those systems.

Open Sourcing

MDM is open-source and development happens in the Eclipse GitLab repositories of the CODECO project. It leverages background assets from IBM-owned repositories that are also open-source. We expect the community to participate in the development of use cases, metadata models and corresponding connectors, with the goal of creating a rich open-source metadata collection environment for systems analysis. All components developed by IBM in the CODECO project, and particularly the MDM module, are licensed under the Apache-2.0 licence, which is considered a permissive license.

3.1.5 SWM: Scheduling and Workload Migration

Summary

SWM handles the initial deployment, monitoring, and potential migration of application workloads within a single cluster and across multi-cluster environments. This means supporting the efficient (low latency, lower power consumption, data sensitivity, *Quality of Experience (QoE)*) placement of applications and their containers across the edge-cloud, derived from information provided either directly by the user or by other components, primarily PDLC (e.g., device and node availability; container centrality; network characteristics), both through a set of *Custom Resources (CR)*. For example, SWM handles the "best" placement (based on context-aware indicators) for the containerised components of an application to be deployed in a cluster, considering the dynamic properties of the available infrastructure, including physical/virtual machines as well as network nodes and links. Furthermore, this placement needs to be dynamically adaptable, which means achieving efficient (low latency, lower power consumption, data sensitivity, QoE) migration of containerised micro-services of an application across edge and cloud.

Value Proposition

Enhanced scheduling and dynamic migration of the workloads (pods) of distributed applications across the cloud-edge continuum, based on QoS and context criteria, completely integrated into the K8s framework.

Open Sourcing

The implementation of SWM is based on background IP from Siemens AG, which has been modified and transferred to the CODECO open-source repository. SWM is released based on Apache-2.0 license.

3.2 CODEF

Summary

The CODECO experimentation framework (CODEF) is a novel microservice-based experimentation tool developed within WP5 and designed to perform CODECO validation and large-scale experimentation, as replacement of EdgeNet. It flexibly covers a diverse range of resources across heterogeneous platforms and infrastructures (AWS, VirtualBox and XCP-ng, VM, physical or bare-metal), providing reproducible deployment of experiments, while covering the entire experimentation process in an automated manner, starting from node allocation from scratch (e.g., deployment and OS) to application installation and reporting of results. CODEF can deploy the complete CODECO OSS, across different infrastructures to test it as a whole or its specific components, allowing the validation of CODECO in different use-cases.

Value Proposition

CODEF will offer shared cluster management capabilities enabling partners to contribute nodes in multi-tenant setups. It can also facilitate federated multi-cluster deployments by simplifying the installation of relevant software, e.g., Liqo and OCM, and also support the deployment of standalone CODECO components for targeted evaluation.

Open Sourcing

CODEF is open source and hosted in the Eclipse GitLab repository of the CODECO project. It is developed by ATH and distributed under the Apache-2.0 license.

3.3 Data Generator

Summary

Data generation, collection, and analysis are crucial for developing accurate Machine Learning (ML) and Decentralized Learning (DL) models, enabling knowledge-driven decision-making. In the Cloud-Edge continuum, data from diverse sources and compute nodes support ML and DL models, driving forecasting, prediction, and clustering. These models support optimizing the Edge-to-Cloud ecosystem, improving energy efficiency, cluster availability, and latency. A key challenge is the limited data available before application deployment and execution. To tackle this, a synthetic data generator has been developed to simulate the output of each CODECO component, generating data for the metrics associated with the application, compute, and network. The generator simulates cross-layer data collection from CODECO components (ACM, MDM, NetMA) and outputs data in a consistent format for analysis.

The Data Generator is an experimentation framework tool, which enriches CODECO components like PDLC with relevant data. It has two main sub-components:

- **The Collector:** Gathers predefined metrics (e.g., CPU, memory) directly from the monitoring engine, using Prometheus, which is ideal for cloud-edge environments and Kubernetes-based applications.
- **The Synthesizer:** Calculates composite metrics (e.g., *MDM-freshness*, *ACM-node_failure*, *ACM-node_sec*) that can't be directly collected by Prometheus, using custom formulas.

The Data Generator simulates the CODECO components (ACM, MDM, NetMA) via CRDs. For experimentation, the generator simulates these components to provide relevant metrics. It includes three controllers, one for each CODECO component, responsible for managing CRDs (*acm-crd.yaml*, *netma-crd.yaml*, *mdm-crd.yaml*) and deployments that track Kubernetes nodes. The output values of the simulated ACM and NetMA components can be found by corresponding CRs using related calls to the k8s REST API. In order to collect the output of MDM, the simulated MDM Controller is built as a REST API Server as well that responds with the MDM CRs, in order to represent the real MDM functionality.

Value Proposition

The synthetic data generator has been developed to simulate the outputs of each CODECO component, offering a reliable solution for system performance testing and validation. By generating data across critical metrics such as application, compute, and network, it provides a comprehensive representation of system behavior, eliminating the need for real-world deployments. This approach enhances performance evaluation and optimization, allowing stakeholders to identify potential issues and refine system configurations in a controlled environment.

Open Sourcing

The Data Generator has been developed by UPRC and is released under the Apache-2.0 license.

3.4 Use-Cases Apps

3.4.1 P1 Smart Monitoring of the Public Infrastructure

Summary

The first use case focuses on the deployment of CODECO to optimize real-time traffic monitoring in urban environments. The use case leverages LiDAR sensors integrated with edge devices to collect and analyse 3D point cloud data, enabling the classification of vehicles and generation of spatio-temporal traffic datasets. By integrating CODECO's task migration capabilities, workloads are dynamically redistributed across nodes within and between clusters to handle high traffic volumes effectively. This ensures uninterrupted and efficient traffic monitoring under various conditions, including peak traffic times. The primary objective is to demonstrate how CODECO can enhance urban traffic management by optimizing computational resources, reducing processing latency, and enabling multi-cluster coordination. Real-world applications include improving traffic flow, providing timely analytics for city planners, and enhancing public safety through better infrastructure monitoring.

Value Proposition

The value proposition of P1 lies in its ability to demonstrate CODECO's capabilities in a real-world traffic monitoring scenario. Key aspects include:

- **Dynamic Resource Allocation:** CODECO's PDLC and SWM components enable real-time task migration to balance computational loads, ensuring continuous operation even during high traffic periods.
- **Scalability:** The system's modular architecture supports seamless integration across multiple nodes and clusters, making it adaptable to a wide range of urban environments.
- **Improved Traffic Analytics:** CODECO facilitates accurate and timely traffic analysis by leveraging LiDAR data, helping city planners make informed decisions to improve urban mobility.

Open Sourcing

All the components developed for this use case, including point cloud processing tools, task migration algorithms, and deployment scripts, are open source. They are licensed under the Apache-2.0 license and accessible in the CODECO project's Eclipse GitLab repository. Additional data handling and Key Performance Indicators (KPI) gathering tools are provided for public use, ensuring transparency and collaboration opportunities.

3.4.2 P2 Vehicular Digital Twin for Safe Urban Mobility

Summary

The second use case involves the implementation of a Vehicular Digital Twin aiming to support a Vulnerable Road User (VRU) protection use case. To do so, it combines Vehicle-to-everything (V2X) technologies altogether with conventional mobile communications in order to periodically gather the position of all road actors involved in the use case. Then, the so-called Digital Twin (DT) tracks the position of all moving actors in the mobility environment to foresee possible risky situations or probable incidents. Once it is done, it issues an alert to prevent something like this to happen. The modules involved in the use case implement a myriad of features, from the capability of processing V2X messages, going through the compression of all the geopositioned measurements in short messages, to the constant loop, which checks for future situations, along with the processing of all gathered information.

Value Proposition

This use case offers the infrastructure deployment of V2X services across an edge-cloud continuum environment, the capability of decentralizing the processing of geopositioned data across multiple nodes, together with the periodic handling of GPS measurements gathered from a mobility scenario to prevent potential incidents.

Open Sourcing

All the functional modules implemented for the current use case are open source, with the peculiarity that some of them import the i2CAT V2X stack solution, which is also open source, but licensed under a more restrictive Affero General Public License (AGPL). Apart from that, all the features will be available for anyone to use, from the data handling to the KPI gathering solution.

3.4.3 P3 MDS across Decentralised Edge-Cloud

Summary

The P3 use case is oriented to **enhance communications in multimedia content distribution services**. This is achieved through the deployment of specific monitoring tools for this type of services, such as user IDs or geographic areas, as well as the collection and prediction of network and computational capacities by the CODECO framework. This use case seeks the integration of the deployed software's own metrics, such as geographic areas or user requests, with CODECO's own information, extracted by ACM and NetMA. In addition, the use of prediction and scheduling tools such as PDLC and SWM will allow the number of caches located on the edge to be optimized, saving both computational and network resources, which can have a great impact on a real network as it is one of the main consumptions by users on a daily basis.

Value Proposition

The added value that the MDS use case brings to CODECO is to demonstrate how this framework can simplify and optimize a traffic management system as widespread in today's networks as an MDS. Among the main points to demonstrate, we can list:

- **Use of open-source tools for the integration of metrics.** Both the code developed in CODECO, and the one used in the use case are based on open-source deployments, the metrics being extracted with protocols such as ALTO or Netperf and with APIs such as MEC. This integration of multiple metrics from open tools and protocols is an incentive for Open-Source collaboration.
- **Modular architecture for scalability.** One of the foundations of CODECO is the use of individual components that reduce dependencies between them, giving greater flexibility to the environment. This flexibility helps the use case to be deployed in different environments with different characteristics, reducing scalability complications.
- **Optimization of the use of network and computing resources.** From AI-based predictions, CODECO manages instantiated resources to optimize communications and resource usage, making the system more efficient and sustainable.

Open Sourcing

All the data created, as well as the code instantiated within the use case, is open source, licensed under the Apache-2.0 license and available in the Eclipse GitLab repository of the CODECO project.

3.4.4 P4 Demand-side Management in Decentralized Grids

Summary

The P4 use case focuses on applying CODECO to optimize **demand-side energy management in decentralized grids**, enhancing energy efficiency and sustainability. CODECO supports the deployment and orchestration of energy applications across edge and cloud environments, using a modular and scalable architecture. The system leverages Internet of Things (IoT) sensors to monitor energy consumption, photovoltaic (PV) generation, and battery levels in real time. Predictive analytics and dynamic task scheduling optimize energy usage, reduce carbon emissions, and balance grid loads effectively. Applications include energy monitoring, forecasting, and dynamic task orchestration, all integrated into the CODECO framework. Key components such as ACM, MDM, PDLC, SWM, and NetMA ensure efficient

deployment, data integration, and fault tolerance. The use case demonstrates CODECO's ability to optimize energy performance across multiple nodes, buildings, and campuses, aligning with global sustainability goals.

Value Proposition

The value proposition of the P4 energy use case lies in its capability to demonstrate CODECO's integration into real-world energy management, fostering scalability, efficiency, and innovation. Key value points include:

1. **Open-Source Accessibility:** The energy management applications and predictive models are open-sourced, fostering reproducibility and collaboration. Docker images for energy monitoring and forecasting are accessible via CODECO repositories, encouraging adoption and integration into similar energy systems.
2. **Modular Architecture for Scalability:** The system's modular design, with distinct CODECO components (e.g., ACM, MDM, PDLC), enables flexible and scalable deployment across edge and cloud environments. This architecture is adaptable to various energy assets, such as PV systems and battery storage.
3. **Energy Optimization through Predictive Analytics:** The integration of advanced predictive models enables proactive load management, ensuring energy demand is met with minimal waste and prioritizing renewable energy utilization.

Open Sourcing

All the data and most of the functional modules implemented for the current use case are open source. Code is available on the CODECO Eclipse GitLab.

3.4.5 P5 Decentralised Wireless AGV Control | Manufacturing

Summary

The P5 use-case focuses on applying CODECO to AGV (Automated Guided Vehicle) fleets in Manufacturing environments to improve the fleet resilience and energy efficiency, via a better distribution of the robotics applications and their micro-services. CODECO assists the deployment of this application via a customized AGV controller dashboard and also the eventual re-scheduling of the application, based on connectivity issues, or node failures. For the use-case, an autonomous AGV navigation app with three micro-services has been developed, based on ROS2: **Bringup**, **SLAM**, and **Navigation**. **Bringup** initializes AGV core systems, setting up communication interfaces, ROS2 nodes, sensors, and actuators. It ensures hardware is operational and enables remote control and visualization via a controller node. **SLAM** enables autonomous driving by mapping environments using Google Cartographer. AGVs (TurtleBots) lack the processing power for SLAM, so a local laptop in the same subnet performs intensive computations. AGVs publish sensor data (laser scans, odometry) via ROS2 topics, which are transmitted to the laptop using DDS. The SLAM Docker image is open sourced on CODECO Dockerhub. **Navigation** uses Nav2 for autonomous movement. The controller node subscribes to AGV data, processes it for mapping, and runs Nav2 for path planning and execution. Nodes like *amcl*, *planner_server* and *controller_server* ensure efficient navigation. AGVs follow predefined waypoints using a Waypoint Follower.

Value Proposition

The value proposition of the P5 robotics app concerns the possibility to use it to test CODECO in mobile automated robots based on the TurtleBot ROS2 package through a proof-of-concept built around modular, scalable microservices. Key value points include:

- **Open-Source Accessibility:** The microservices (*Bringup*, *SLAM*, and *Navigation*) and respective Docker images are open-sourced and accessible via the CODECO GitLab and the CODECO Dockerhub, fostering reproducibility, collaboration, and integration with other systems.
- **Modular Architecture for Scalability:** The use of distinct microservices (*Bringup*, *SLAM*, *Navigation*) and Kubernetes for task orchestration makes the system flexible, scalable, and easy to adapt for different robotic platforms and environments.
- **Robust Navigation and Autonomy based on far Edge principles:** The integration of advanced navigation algorithms (*Nav2*) and tools like *Waypoint Follower* with a Turtle-based application provides the grounds to test CODECO in far Edge environments.
- **Persistent Data Accessibility:** The use of K8s PV/PVC ensures critical data like maps remain available, enabling new nodes to take over seamlessly without data loss, reinforcing operational resilience.

Open Sourcing

Code and documentation copyright 2024 fortiss GmbH, under the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) license. Documentation is licensed under CC. Code is available on the CODECO Eclipse GitLab³.

3.4.6 P6 Automated Crownstone Application Deployment for Smart Buildings

Summary

In Use Case P6, the focus lies on applying CODECO in the deployment and orchestration of edge applications in smart offices. The basic technology applied in the use case is the Crownstone technology developed by ALM. Miniaturized hardware devices called Crownstone nodes are built into the power outlets of a building. They can switch on and off devices connected to their power outlet, they can measure the power consumption of those devices, form a mesh network with other Crownstone nodes to communicate, they can be attached to external Bluetooth-enabled sensors and actuators, and, finally, they are capable of running small programs on their processor, called micro-apps. Furthermore, the network of Crownstone nodes enables indoor localisation of people and devices; together with Crownstone hubs (Raspberry Pi devices extended with special Universal Serial Bus (USB) Crownstone nodes), they form an edge network where applications can be deployed. Finally, a Crownstone cloud component enables the buildup of history around the usage of the office by people and the power consumption of devices in the office.

Value Proposition

CODECO is used in this use case to ease the deployment and reconfiguration of applications in the Crownstone network. In particular, the focus is put in the following aspects:

³ <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/use-cases/p5-amr-manufacturing>

- **Extreme far edge involvement:** Automated deployment enabled via Kubernetes even up to the level of the individual Crownstone nodes, which are involved by means of proxy worker nodes called Virtual Kubelet.
- **Topology-based (re)deployment:** The Crownstone network is capable of informing CODECO about changes in its hardware topology, e.g. the addition or removal of a Crownstone node in the network, based on which CODECO can decide to alter de application configuration in the network.
- **Occupancy-based (re)deployment:** The indoor localisation and occupancy information can (either directly or indirectly) be utilized by CODECO for maintaining the desired state of deployment based on the presence of people or occupancy density levels.

Open Sourcing

The Crownstone node firmware is completely open source and currently published in GitHub⁴. Software development done for the P6 use case is open source as well and available in the CODECO Eclipse Gitlab⁵.

⁴ <https://github.com/crownstone>

⁵ <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/use-cases/p5-amr-manufacturing>

4 Implementing Open Collaboration Best Practices

During the first year of the project life, the partners in charge of development designed the CODECO architecture and implemented an initial version of the CODECO Open-source Toolkit, and consequently the work around this code was devoted to setting up the environment and paving the ground for open collaboration. During the second year, the CODECO Open-source Toolkit has reached its maturity phase, the software development work in CODECO continued as expected and the Research Labs repository took good shape, allowing ECL partner to help with the IP work around the code and the repository, following the open-source good practices.

The application of the open-source best practices has been translated into statements which have been put into practice in CODECO, among which the following ones can be highlighted:

- All the CODECO repositories in Research Labs should be public. No work in private is allowed in the public repository, as well as all the issues and discussions should be public.
- All the CODECO repositories should have a *Readme* file, facilitating the engagement and adoption of the CODECO code by external developers.
- All the CODECO source code files (when the programming language allows it) will have a copyright header, following the structure explained in Section 4.2.1.
- All the CODECO components will use open-source libraries, and the 3rd party library conflicts or issues will be solved by the developers.

The first three points are covered under Section 4.2.2, as they correspond strictly to *best practices*, while the last one is not rigorously a *best practice* but corresponds to an *IP potential issue*, and therefore is covered in Section 4.3.2.

4.1 Open Collaboration – Eclipse Research Labs

Open (and transparent) collaboration is one of the pillars of open source. Collaborative development in the CODECO public repository started at an early stage of the project. The CODECO developers joined forces since the beginning, and, by the end of the first year, 35 developers had joined the members in the CODECO Research Labs in Gitlab. It continued to grow, and at the end of year 2 there is a mass of 51 developers. This development materialised in an initial snapshot of the CODECO open-source toolkit released in M10 (*D11 - CODECO Basic Operation and Open Toolkit v1.0* [4]) and a stable version of the same released in M18 (*D12 - CODECO Basic Operation and Open Toolkit v2.0* [5]).

4.1.1 Research Labs

Eclipse Research Labs is a combination of infrastructure (GitLab), processes and trainings to implement open-source best practices right from the start and increase the chances of delivering high-quality, professional open-source results (see also the deliverable *D10 – CODECO Technological Guidelines, Reference Architecture, and Open-source Ecosystem Design v2.0* [3]).

Eclipse Research Labs aims at gradually and continuously preparing research results to become proper open-source projects during the research project lifetime.

At the beginning of the project, in month M2, the Eclipse CODECO Research Labs in GitLab⁶ was provisioned. Since that moment, developers have received access to it: 51 developers have signed the *Eclipse Contributor Agreement (ECA)* and joined the CODECO GitLab during the first two years of project lifetime (35 developers registered during the first twelve months and 17 between month M13 and M24).

In the Research Labs, as in any other GitLab project, two types of entities can be found:

- A subgroup, which allows to manage the members which have access to the content inside but does not host code.
- A project, which is the equivalent of a sub-repository, where the code is hosted. A project under another higher-level project may be called a subproject.

Specifically, the CODECO repository is structured following the components of the Open-source Toolkit (see Figure 3) along with some other specific subprojects:

- One subgroup per CODECO component (ACM, MDM, NetMA, PDLC and SWM).
- One subgroup named “*Experimentation Framework and Demonstration*”, which hosts the CODECO datasets, a data generator to allow to run CODECO components and integration and experimentation tools (see Figure 4).
- One subgroup devoted to the CODECO Use Cases, containing code specific of each Pilot (see Figure 5).
- A last sub-project called “*gitlab-profile*” which contains scripts to test the CODECO components along with integration scripts and the instructions to deploy the CODECO framework in your machine and in a Docker container.

The screenshot shows the GitLab interface for the CODECO Project. The page title is "CODECO Project" with a description: "Cognitive, cross-layer and highly adaptive Edge-Cloud management framework". Below the title, there are tabs for "Subgroups and projects", "Shared projects", and "Inactive". A search bar is present with the text "Search (3 character minimum)". The main content area lists several subgroups and projects:

Entity	Name	Members	Projects	Issues
Subgroup	Experimentation Framework and Demonstrations	2	1	1
Subgroup	Metadata Manager - MDM	0	3	1
Subgroup	Network Management and Adaptation - NetMA	0	3	1
Subgroup	Privacy-preserving Decentralised Learning and Context-awareness - PDLC	1	3	1
Subgroup	Scheduling and Workload Migration - SWM	0	2	3
Subgroup	Use-Cases	2	5	4
Project	Automated Configuration Management - ACM	4 stars		1 hour ago
Project	gitlab-profile	0 stars		58 minutes ago

Figure 3. The CODECO Research Labs GitLab.

⁶ <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project>

... / CODECO Project / Experimentation Framework and Demonstrations

E Experimentation Framework and Demonstrations

Subgroups and projects Shared projects Inactive

🔄 Search (3 character minimum) Name

1															
<div style="display: flex; align-items: center;"> <div style="margin-right: 5px;">▼</div> <div style="display: flex; align-items: center;"> 1															
0		1 week ago													
1		2 weeks ago													
0		2 weeks ago													

Figure 4. The Experimentation Framework and Demonstrations sub-group.

Eclipse Research Labs / CODECO Project / Use-Cases

U Use-Cases

Subgroups and projects Shared projects Inactive

🔄 Search (3 character minimum) Name

<div style="display: flex; align-items: center;"> <div style="margin-right: 5px;">></div> <div style="display: flex; align-items: center;"> 1																			
<div style="display: flex; align-items: center;"> <div style="margin-right: 5px;">></div> <div style="display: flex; align-items: center;"> 3																			
0		6 days ago																	
0		6 days ago																	
0		5 days ago																	
0		4 days ago																	

Figure 5. Use-Cases sub-group.

Eclipse Research Labs not only hosts the CODECO open-source repository but allows the developer to have access to a *wiki*⁷ page which details the open-source good practices recommended to be followed in software development.

Lastly, Continuous Integration and Continuous Development (CI/CD) procedures are implemented under the scope of WP3. Every time there is a relevant code update, through a merge request in any of the CODECO sub-repositories, the pipelines are executed in Runners⁸,

⁷ <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/groups/eclipse-research-labs/-/wikis/home>

⁸ <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/groups/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/-/runners>

building a new image of the CODECO Toolkit. A general look of the pipelines corresponding to CODECO project can be seen in the Figure 6.

The screenshot shows the GitLab Runners interface for the CODECO project. At the top, it displays 'Eclipse Research Labs / CODECO Project / Runners'. The main heading is 'Runners', with a 'Fleet dashboard' link and a 'New group runner' button. Below this, there are filters for 'All 3', 'Group 0', and 'Project 3'. A search bar and a 'Show only inherited' toggle are also present. A summary row shows: Online 3, Offline 0, Stale 0, Upgrade available 0, and Upgrade recommended 3. The main table lists three runners:

Status	Runner configuration	Owner
Online (Idle)	#2106 (-vzG2Vsr) Project Version 17.5.3 · icom-runner-codeco Last contact: 17 minutes ago · 146.124.106.227 · 444 Created by Konstantinos Karageorgos 4 weeks ago icom-runner icom-runner-codeco	P3 - MEC Enablement
Online (Idle)	#2103 (D8Rbt2-D) Project Last contact: 40 minutes ago · 3.78.140.226 · 70 Created by Dean Kelly 1 month ago rhat-runner	Automated Configuration Management - ACM
Online (Idle)	#1782 (yzhyPixB) Project Version 17.0.0 · sie-acc-gw Last contact: 5 minutes ago · 62.156.206.40 · 251 Created by Jürgen Geßwein 6 months ago	Workload Placement Solver

Figure 6. Pipelines in GitLab Runners corresponding to the CODECO project.

4.1.2 Development Process

In order to implement *open collaboration* as an open-source best practice, the CODECO developers have used an AGILE methodology, working with issues or tickets, boards and continuous follow up. This methodology allows not only tracking of the progress and assignment of responsibilities but enables direct and quick communication among partners on specific matters or issues. The next two figures show snapshots of the CODECO issue list (see Figure 7) and issue board (see Figure 8) at the time of writing this deliverable.

Eclipse Research Labs / CODECO Project / Issues

Open 44 Closed 77 All 121 Select project to create issue

Search or filter results... Created date

- integration-test.sh: Failing ping test and missing underlay topology**
eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/network-management-and-adaptation-netma/secure-connectivity#2 · created 2 days ago by Yanlong Huang updated 13 hours ago
- package installation required for netma tests**
eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/gitlab-profile#11 · created 4 days ago by Konstantinos Karageorgos
Enhancement
- MDM test script does not provide correct portability**
eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/gitlab-profile#10 · created 4 days ago by Konstantinos Karageorgos updated 4 days ago
- CODECO Requirements**
eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/gitlab-profile#9 · created 1 week ago by Panagiotis Karamolegkos
Documentation **Enhancement** **High Priority** updated 1 week ago
- Ingress traffic from MDM to Prometheus svc**
eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/acm#24 · created 1 week ago by dalal ali updated 2 days ago
Bug **K3s**
- Multi-arch support**
eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/metadata-manager-mdm/mdm-api#4 · created 1 week ago by dalal ali updated 1 week ago
Help Wanted **Important**
- Generalize CODECO installation for all K8s environments**
eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/acm#23 · created 2 weeks ago by Konstantinos Karageorgos updated 2 days ago
Help Wanted **Important**
- [PDLC-DP] Remove copy models Code** 1 of 2 checklist items completed
eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/pdlc-deployment#29 · created 2 weeks ago by Panagiotis Karamolegkos updated 2 days ago
Low Priority **UPRC** **Work In Progress**
- [PDLC-RL / PDLC-DP] Copy models to Volume from RL**
eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/pdlc-deployment#27 · created 2 weeks ago by Panagiotis Karamolegkos updated 2 weeks ago
i2CAT **Low Priority**
- [Installation Error] err="couldn't get resource list for metrics.k8s.io/v1beta1: the server is currently unable to handle the** updated 2 weeks ago

Figure 7. Most recent issues currently open in CODECO Research Labs.

Eclipse Research Labs / CODECO Project / Issue Boards

Development Search

Open 38 0

- [Docker Container Installation] Unable to Delete Cluster (Bug, Enhancement, Help Wanted) acm #19
- Fix Building of Container Images (Bug) qos-scheduler #4
- Deprecated License (IP Review) pdlc-rl #1
- License missing (IP Review) acm #6
- PDLC not writing nodeRecommendation in the SWM CR (High Priority, KinD) acm #25
- after_netma_deployment.sh script issue (Bug) acm #14
- typo in scripts/post_deploy.sh

Closed 66 0

- [Documentation] CODECO Application YAML Structure (Documentation, Enhancement) gitlab-profile #5
- NetMa components on arm64/v8 (Bug, KinD) secure-connectivity #1
- [PDLC - GNN | WP3] 8 Node Model (ICOM, Use Case Related, Validation) pdlc-deployment #20
- [PDLC-GNN / PDLC-DP] Copy models to Volume from GNNs (ICOM, Low Priority, Validation) pdlc-deployment #28
- [kustomize Error] make: command: Command not found (Bug, KinD) gitlab-profile #7
- [Documentation] CODECO Application's Logs (Documentation, Enhancement) gitlab-profile #2

Figure 8. Current status of the issue board in CODECO Research Labs.

These issues, where the discussions and work take place, are public and are available in the CODECO Research Labs Issue List⁹ and Issue Board¹⁰, at project level and a CODECO component level as well. Whoever visits the project and reads the issues will have an idea of the work put behind this code and project, generating trust while feeding and respecting our community (see section 2.2.4).

⁹ https://gitlab.eclipse.org/groups/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/-/issues/?sort=popularity&state=opened&first_page_size=100

¹⁰ <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/groups/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/-/boards>

4.2 Copyright Headers and Repository Best Practices

4.2.1 Copyright Headers

According to the open-source best practices, appropriate **copyright headers** should be added to all relevant files in the repositories accordingly. Copyright headers for CODECO are intended to follow the Eclipse Foundation recommendations as described in the Eclipse Foundation Project Handbook¹¹ and depicted in Figure 9. The headers consider the following fields:

- 1) Name of the initial copyright owner (this must be a legal entity); other organisations that have contributed are either listed individually or grouped together by appending "and others". The year is expressed either as a single year or a range spanning the year of the initial creation and that of the most recent change.
- 2) Declared project licenses described in human readable form.
- 3) Declared project licenses indicated using SPDX codes and expressions.
- 4) The names of the contributors and the nature of their contribution (this section is optional and may be excluded).

```

/*****
 * Copyright (c) {year} {owner}[ and others] ❶
 *
 * This program and the accompanying materials are made available under the ❷
 * terms of the Eclipse Public License 2.0 which is available at
 * http://www.eclipse.org/legal/epl-2.0.
 *
 * SPDX-License-Identifier: EPL-2.0 ❸
 *
 * Contributors: ❹
 *   {name} - initial API and implementation
 *****/

```

Figure 9. Copyright header in the CODECO OSS code.

During the second reporting period, ECL has developed two new tools which, among other functionalities, measure the usage of Copyright headers in the source code files present in the CODECO repository and add a Copyright header when it is missing. These two tools, *Add License*¹² and *BP Check*¹³, are open source and are available in the Research Repository¹⁴ under the Eclipse Research Labs.

4.2.2 Repository Best Practices Implementation

During the second year, ECL has iteratively applied the tools enabling the implementation of the best practice in the CODECO Research Labs and, as result, the condition of the repository from an open-source perspective has been enhanced. This section shows the current status of this project regarding the three points mentioned in Section 0: repository visibility, availability of *README* files and utilisation of copyright headers.

¹¹ <https://www.eclipse.org/projects/handbook/#ip-copyright-headers>

¹² <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/research-eclipse/add-license>

¹³ <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/research-eclipse/bp-check>

¹⁴ <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/research-eclipse>

Firstly, all the CODECO sub-repositories are set as public, being available to external developers, and have updated the *README* file, as depicted in Table 1.

Table 1. CODECO repositories visibility, license used and presence of Readme file.

CODECO Subproject	Visibility	License	Readme file
acm	Public	Apache-2.0	README.md
experimentation-framework-and-demonstrations/data-generators-and-datasets/synthetic-data-generator	Public	Apache-2.0	README.md
experimentation-framework-and-demonstrations/experimentation-framework	Public	Apache-2.0	README.md
metadata-manager-mdm/connectors	Public	Apache-2.0	README.md
metadata-manager-mdm/graphdb	Public	Apache-2.0	README.md
metadata-manager-mdm/mdm-api	Public	Apache-2.0	README.md
network-management-and-adaptation-netma/network-exposure	Public	Apache-2.0	README.md
network-management-and-adaptation-netma/network-state-management	Public	Apache-2.0	README.md
network-management-and-adaptation-netma/network-state-management-/tree/main/netma-nsm-mon	Public	Apache-2.0	README.md
network-management-and-adaptation-netma/network-state-management-/tree/main/netma-nsm-npp	Public	Apache-2.0	README.md
network-management-and-adaptation-netma/secure-connectivity	Public	Apache-2.0	README.md
privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/pdlc-ca	Public	Apache-2.0	README.md
privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/pdlc-deployment	Public	Apache-2.0	README.md
privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/PDLC-DL/mlops	Public	Apache-2.0	README.md
privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/PDLC-DL/pdlc-gnns	Public	Apache-2.0	README.md
privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/PDLC-DL/pdlc-rl	Public	Apache-2.0	README.md
privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/pdlc-dp	Public	Apache-2.0	README.md
scheduling-and-workload-migration-swm/qos-scheduler	Public	Apache-2.0 CC-BY-SA-4.0	README.md

CODECO Subproject	Visibility	License	Readme file
scheduling-and-workload-migration-swm/workload-placement-solver	Public	Apache-2.0 CC-BY-SA-4.0	README.md
use-cases/p1-smartcity	Public	-	README.md
use-cases/p2-vehicularadt	Public	AGPL-3.0	README.md
use-cases/p3-mec-enablement	Public	Apache-2.0	README.md
use-cases/p4-dem-energy	Public	-	README.md
use-cases/p5-amr-manufacturing	Public	Apache-2.0	README.md
use-cases/p6-crownstonesmartbuildings	Public	-	README.md

Secondly, regarding copyright headers, most of the repositories are using copyright headers in their source code files, therefore identifying the entity which owns the copyright for the file. The six CODECO Use Cases have been added more recently to the repository, and at the time of writing the deliverable they are still working on implementing the open-source best practices.

Table 2, shows the copyright owner, declared in the copyright headers, and the percentage of source code files including a copyright header for each corresponding CODECO sub-repository.

Table 2. Copyright owners for the CODECO repositories and % of files including a header.

CODECO Subproject	% copyright headers	Copyright Owners
acm	97%	Red Hat Inc.
experimentation-framework-and-demonstrations/data-generators-and-datasets/synthetic-data-generator	79%	University of Piraeus Research Centre Telefónica Innovación Digital
experimentation-framework-and-demonstrations/experimentation-framework	35%	Athena RC Others
metadata-manager-mdm/connectors	89%	IBM Corp.
metadata-manager-mdm/graphdb	100%	IBM Corp.
metadata-manager-mdm/mdm-api	91%	IBM Corp.
network-management-and-adaptation-netma/network-exposure	39%	Telefónica Innovación Digital Others
network-management-and-adaptation-netma/network-state-management	41%	Others
network-management-and-adaptation-netma/network-state-management/-/tree/main/netma-nsm-mon	41%	fortiss GmbH
network-management-and-adaptation-netma/network-state-management/-	41%	

CODECO Subproject	% copyright headers	Copyright Owners
<u>/tree/main/netma-nsm-npp</u>		
<u>network-management-and-adaptation-netma/secure-connectivity</u>	13%	Others
<u>privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/pdlc-ca</u>	92%	fortiss GmbH
<u>privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/pdlc-deployment</u>	100%	University of Piraeus Research Centre
<u>privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/PDLC-DL/mlops</u>	100%	Intracom Telecom
<u>privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/PDLC-DL/pdlc-gnns</u>	64%	Intracom Telecom
<u>privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/PDLC-DL/pdlc-rl</u>	94%	Siemens AG I2CAT Foundation
<u>privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/pdlc-dp</u>	94%	University of Piraeus Research Centre I2CAT Foundation Siemens AG
<u>scheduling-and-workload-migration-swm/qos-scheduler</u>	88%	UC3M Siemens AG Others
<u>scheduling-and-workload-migration-swm/workload-placement-solver</u>	75%	Siemens AG
<u>use-cases/p1-smartcity</u>	0%	-
<u>use-cases/p2-vehicularadt</u>	50%	I2CAT Foundation
<u>use-cases/p3-mec-enablement</u>	59%	Intracom Telecom
<u>use-cases/p4-dem-energy</u>	0%	-
<u>use-cases/p5-amr-manufacturing</u>	65%	fortiss GmbH Others
<u>use-cases/p6-crownstonesmartbuildings</u>	97%	Red Hat Inc.

4.3 OSS Licenses and IP Validation

4.3.1 OSS Licenses in CODECO

As discussed in Section 2, IP and license management is an important part of open-source software development. Two steps need to be considered:

- The license(s) under which the CODECO open-source components are made available. This license regulates the way other developers use the CODECO Toolkit.
- Compatibility with the licenses of third-party libraries used by CODECO components. These licenses regulate the use of other software in CODECO.

The initial basic agreement for CODECO open source is that it would be licensed under a permissive or weak copyleft license. By default, this includes Apache-2.0, MIT, Berkeley Software Distribution (BSD)-3-Clause, and EPL-2.0. The use of other licenses was not initially recommended but would be decided based on prior discussion among the consortium members. By the time of releasing the first version of the CODECO Toolkit, in M18, it was agreed by the CODECO component leaders and developers that, in general, all the CODECO components would be licensed under Apache-2.0. It was presented at a CODECO General Assembly as showed in Figure 10.

Figure 10. All the CODECO components and sub-components licensed under Apache-2.0.

The utilisation of one unique license for the whole CODECO Toolkit is not a coincidence. Licensing a project under only one license shows consistency and is an open-source best practice. Moreover, if that open-source license is a well-known business-friendly license, such as Apache-2.0, external developers will not be concerned about the use of the code in this repository but will feel comfortable, with the main goal of fostering adoption.

The CODECO repository, as every other software repository, includes the source code files and the corresponding documentation. Some of this documentation in the CODECO Research Labs has been licensed under Creative Commons 4.0, CC-BY-SA-4.0.

On the other hand, in the CODECO Research Labs, the five CODECO components can be found, which represent the core of the CODECO Toolkit, as well as the six use cases. The CODECO use cases are not considered part of the CODECO Open-source Toolkit *per se*. They consume it and represent six applications of the CODECO Toolkit. Therefore, the code in those repositories may be licensed under another open-source license, different from Apache-2.0.

4.3.2 IP Validation

3rd-party license compliance is checked semi-automatically on a regular basis, using an appropriate tool developed by the Eclipse Foundation. At the beginning of the project, the *Eclipse Dash License Tool*¹⁵ (short: Dash License) was being used. Dash License identifies the licenses of content and is intended primarily for use by Eclipse committers to vet third party content used by their Eclipse open-source project. During the second year of CODECO, the Eclipse Foundation has developed a new tool, the *IP Check Tool*¹⁶. It offers the same functionalities as the original *Dash License*, improving usability and scalability, while adding some extra features.

None of these two tools identifies dependencies (at least not in general). Rather, the value they provide starts once the list of dependencies is identified by build tools. The tools are as good as the input provided, and it is up to the committer to ensure that the input, the list of dependencies, is correct. That means, dependencies which are not automatically discovered by build tools must be vetted manually.

For any license-incompatible library found, the developer of the respective CODECO component is asked to exchange it, i.e., looking for a library providing similar functionality under a compatible license.

ECL has iteratively applied the *IP Check Tool*, having analysed a total of 3426 dependencies (3rd party libraries used) in the CODECO repository. An automatic report is generated, as shown in Figure 11, which indicates:

- Location: file which indicates the library generating the potentially problematic 3rd party library.
- Name: library used in the CODECO code which potentially causes the issue.
- License: license under which the 3rd party library is licensed.
- Status: status of the dependency according to the corresponding authority.
- Authority: entity assessing how the 3rd party library used is properly licensed under an open-source license and follows the open-source best practices; normally it will be Clearly Defined¹⁷ or the Eclipse Management Organization¹⁸ (EMO).
- Verification: In case the status is “restricted”, result of a manual verification.

¹⁵ <https://github.com/eclipse/dash-licenses>

¹⁶ <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/research-eclipse/ip-check>

¹⁷ <https://clearlydefined.io/>

¹⁸ <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipsefdn/emo-team>

IP Check Report

Export All Search

Location	Name	License	Status	Authority	Verification
eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/PDLC-DL/pdlc-gnns/STGNN_controller/inference/requirements.txt	pypi/pypi-/flask/3.0.0	BSD-2-Clause AND BSD-3-Clause	approved	clearlydefined	-
eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/PDLC-DL/pdlc-gnns/STGNN_controller/inference/requirements.txt	pypi/pypi-/kubernetes/27.2.0	Apache-2.0	approved	clearlydefined	-
eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/PDLC-DL/pdlc-gnns/STGNN_controller/inference/requirements.txt	pypi/pypi-/numpy/1.23.5	BSD-2-Clause	restricted	clearlydefined	verified
eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/PDLC-DL/pdlc-gnns/STGNN_controller/inference/requirements.txt	pypi/pypi-/pandas/2.0.3	BSD-2-Clause AND BSD-3-Clause	restricted	clearlydefined	verified
eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/PDLC-DL/pdlc-gnns/STGNN_controller/inference/requirements.txt	pypi/pypi-/requests-oauthlib/1.3.1	BSD-2-Clause AND ISC	restricted	clearlydefined	verified
eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/PDLC-DL/pdlc-gnns/STGNN_controller/inference/requirements.txt	pypi/pypi-/requests/2.31.0	Apache-2.0 AND MIT AND Apache-2.0	approved	#13074	-
eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/PDLC-DL/pdlc-gnns/STGNN_controller/orchestrator/requirements.txt	pypi/pypi-/kubernetes/27.2.0	Apache-2.0	approved	clearlydefined	-
eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/PDLC-DL/pdlc-gnns/STGNN_controller/orchestrator/requirements.txt	pypi/pypi-/numpy/1.23.5	BSD-2-Clause	restricted	clearlydefined	verified
eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/PDLC-DL/pdlc-gnns/STGNN_controller/orchestrator/requirements.txt	pypi/pypi-/pandas/2.0.3	BSD-2-Clause AND BSD-3-Clause	restricted	clearlydefined	verified
eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/PDLC-DL/pdlc-gnns/STGNN_controller/orchestrator/requirements.txt	pypi/pypi-/requests/2.31.0	Apache-2.0 AND MIT AND Apache-2.0	approved	#13074	-

Figure 11. Snapshot of the report analysing the dependencies in the CODECO code.

Out of those 3426 dependencies, just 5 required further work. For each one, an issue was created in CODECO Research Labs and assigned to the developer, following the procedure explained above. The 5 issues in the repository are listed in Figure 12. The developers reviewed the issues and looked for a solution. In some cases, updating the library to the latest version or moving to an alternative library, in case the used one is deprecated, can solve the issue. Most of the issues were resolved and closed, while some of them correspond to work in progress.

As the software development in CODECO goes on, the CODECO code continues to evolve, and therefore the IP validation will be in progress until the end of the project.

Eclipse Research Labs / CODECO Project / Issues

Open 2 Closed 3 All 5 Select project to create issue

- License missing** 0 of 1 checklist item completed
eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/acm#6 · created 3 months ago by David Remon
updated 4 weeks ago
IP Review
- Archived Library. Not maintained** 1 of 1 checklist item completed
eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/experimentation-framework-and-demonstrations/experimentation-framework#2 · created 3 months ago by David Remon
closed 3 weeks ago
IP Review
- Archived Library. Not maintained** 1 of 1 checklist item completed
eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/scheduling-and-workload-migration-swm/qos-scheduler#3 · created 3 months ago by David Remon
closed 1 week ago
IP Review
- Deprecated License** 0 of 1 checklist item completed
eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/PDLC-DL/pdlc-rl#1 · created 3 months ago by David Remon
updated 1 week ago
IP Review
- Deprecated library** 1 of 1 checklist item completed
eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/experimentation-framework-and-demonstrations/experimentation-framework#1 · created 3 months ago by David Remon
closed 1 month ago
IP Review

Figure 12. Issues in the CODECO Research Labs corresponding to IP dependencies.

4.4 Trainings

To facilitate the open-source work to the partners and to help understand the open-source best practices, OSS trainings are provided to the CODECO consortium. While during the first reporting period (M7 to M12) three OSS trainings were provided, summarized in Table 3, during the second period (M13 to M24) the focus has been brought to the implementation of the open-source best practices, and, therefore, there has not been any additional training.

During the last year of the project, more attention will be put to the exploitation of the CODECO OSS Toolkit, as explained in Section 6, and one training about open-source business models will be provided.

Table 3. Training on open-source best practices provided to CODECO consortium in 2023.

Name	Topics	Date
Open-source Ecosystem	Introduction to the main aspects of doing successful open-source including governance, IP and license management, community building, and infrastructure for open collaboration; best practices from experience in doing open-source in research projects	February 2023
Open-source Licensing and Compliance	Introduction to open-source software licenses; categories of OSS licenses and major features; license compliance and compatibility; recommendations for CODECO open-source components	June 2023

Open Collaboration, Open Development	Open collaboration; Intellectual Property and Copyright; how to develop in the Eclipse open-source ecosystem through Research Labs	November 2023
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5 OSS Community-building Year 2

This section summarises the community-building activities done during the second reporting period, while T7.1 was active: M13 – M24.

During the initial phase, the main goal was to set up the infrastructure to allow the consortium to develop in an open and collaborative way. During this second phase, the main objective has been to start implementing the open-source best practices while community-building activities have been developed, focussing on starting the gathering of a community around CODECO, with the strong intention to make an impact with the open source. A key step into this direction, although not strictly a WP7 activity, was taken in WP3, when the CODECO Toolkit was completely specified (see deliverable D10 [3]) and the framework architecture was fully defined.

The CODECO results comprise five major assets of which three are most relevant for the open-source and community-building approach:

- **A2 Open-source Eclipse Repository:** A developer-oriented open-source software repository, to be available in an early stage of the project, thus allowing for early exploitation of initial, advanced results and a better adaptation throughout the project lifetime.
- **A3 Training Database:** Training tools and events, to support the development of services based on the CODECO framework.
- **A5 Innovation and Research Community Engagement Programme:** Multiple community events, based on the different use-cases and including the different CODECO stakeholders.

Section 0 explained how the CODECO open repository has been set up in the Eclipse Research Labs, in Gitlab. Along with it, to facilitate the adoption of the open-source approach by the project partners, several trainings have been provided. These actions have addressed the first two assets, A2 and A3, while A5 will be addressed in this section, where we will list the actions done with the main goal of engaging with the developers and creating a community around CODECO. This includes the following activities as described in Task 7.1:

- **Development of liaisons with relevant open-source projects and initiatives**, along with the interaction with the EUCloudEdgeIoT¹⁹ Research Community, as well as other European initiatives, such as HiPEAC²⁰, and AIOTI²¹.
- **Participation in OSS community events**, e.g., Open Community Experience (OCX) 2024²² (former EclipseCon), DevConf 2024²³.
- **Production of open-source specific communication materials** (logo, posters, stickers, etc.), contribution to the relevant channels (social media, blog, Eclipse newsletter) and preparation of future events such as the CODECO Demo Camp/Hackathon (M31).

These task objectives have been addressed, as will be shown in section 5.2, where the communication activities and events done during this second year are displayed. The Hackathon/Demo Camp was planned to take place at the end of year 2 (M21-M22). However, it has been finally postponed until summer of the next year, allowing the CODECO Toolkit to be

¹⁹ <https://eucloudedgeiot.eu/>

²⁰ <https://www.hipeac.net/>

²¹ <https://aioti.eu/>

²² <https://www.ocxconf.org/event/778b82cc-6834-48a4-a58e-f883c5a7b8c9/home>

²³ <https://www.devconf.info/cz/>

in a mature status and facilitating the approach to the community. It will be explained in the next version of this deliverable (D26, due M36). Section 5.1 puts the CODECO target groups in the perspective of open source.

5.1 Target Communities

CODECO has defined in its GA the target stakeholders. For the purpose of outreach, the CODECO Deliverable *D21 – Dissemination, Communication, Promotion Plan* [6] explains the key activities planned for each target stakeholder group. These groups, from their own perspectives, may be interested in the open-source part of the project:

- **Information and communication technologies (ICT):** Industrial and small and medium-sized enterprises (SME) players; vendors and integrators, service providers and telecommunications operators.
For ICT companies, open source is a means to save money, resources, attract developers and foster innovation. ICT will keep an eye on the available open-source tools for their own projects, products, or services.
- **Government, municipalities, public authorities, and policymakers (GOV):** A wide group of public sector stakeholders including government agencies, regulators, municipalities, citizens, public authorities, and other organizations.
For GOV, it is important to build knowledge regarding open-source to address the need for vendor-neutral public infrastructure, to avoid vendor-lock in and reach some degree of digital sovereignty.
- **Standardization entities and open-source communities (SDO):** Standardization entities responsible for defining and maintaining standards for various industries and technologies.
Normative, pre-normative entities and with open-source alliances and consortia will collaborate on the development and adoption of innovative technologies and open-source software, relevant to the CODECO ecosystem.
- **Academia and research (AR):** Research scientists, teachers, and students in the field of computer science, engineering, and related disciplines. AR are a key group to spread the benefits of the CODECO concept.
It is key to educate the next generation IT experts and equip them with the open-source skills required for careers in industry and academia alike. CODECO will be a vehicle to perform this kind of education and vice-versa benefit from the innovation potential that is inherent to this stakeholder group.
- **End-users (EUS):** The public and specific end-users in the use-case domains, including consumers, who are interested in learning about the latest developments in Edge-Cloud computing and IoT and how these technologies will impact their lives.
CODECO open-source results may be exploited in future products or services for EUS. It allows them to freely experiment with the latest innovations.
- **Developers (DEV):** Software developers and early developers with whom CODECO shall interact via the activities developed in, among others, WP7 (community-building, Innovation and Research Community Engagement Programme for third-party engagement) will be considered to promote and evaluate the CODECO toolkit and accelerate the integration of knowledge.
Software developers are the key target group when aiming to build a community of open-source developers around CODECO.
- **Public in General (Pub):** General audience may also be considered as stakeholders of CODECO. Even without a specialized background in the technical areas of the project, they may still be interested in CODECO and understanding its potential implications for society.

Evangelizing about open-source and creating interest and knowledge in the general public is important and doing so by communicating about publicly funded innovations such as CODECO is a must.

Among these groups, defined as target audience, the community-building activities are developed with the focus on two groups, **open-source communities (SDO)** and **developers (DEV)** and keeping in mind also the other relevant groups as **ICT, GOV** or **EUS**.

We have already put effort explaining it in this document in Section 2: open source is inherently linked to software developers since it started; the creators of open source were software developers (**DEV**), and this group requires special attention. When it comes to our CODECO research project, the same principle applies: “*Don’t forget the developers.*” This group has the capacity of making CODECO sustainable.

Most of the open-source communication activities and events done in CODECO so far, have been focused on the developers, trying to generate awareness about the CODECO Toolkit. The following section provides an overview of the measures implemented so far, focussing specifically on the current reporting period M13-M24.

5.2 Community-building Activities and Impact

This section provides an overview on the community-building activities developed until M24.

Table 4 summarises the main activities performed in CODECO during the project’s first two years, under the “community-building” umbrella, with special focus to the ones implemented between M12 and M24, as the activities during M1-M12 had already been duly reported in the previous version of this document.

Typically, open-source community activities contribute to a range of communication and dissemination categories and related KPIs as explained in the CODECO Deliverable *D21 – Dissemination, Communication, Promotion Plan* [6]. The next table shows, among the dissemination activities for the CODECO project, their measures of impact listed in that Deliverable, the specific KPIs regarding open-source and the contribution to them from the open-source perspective.

Table 4. Open-source community-building activities held until M24.

Dissemination Activity	Targets	Aim	KPIs (D21)	Lead/ Contributors	Open-source contributions, year 1 and year 2	Impact
Media dissemination	All	Dissemination of the overall project development via broad media, e.g., TV, podcasts, YouTube videos, public magazines, and journals.	1 per year	FOR, ECL, INO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Website (INO, FOR). - Involvement in EUCEI (open-source, ECL, FOR). - EclipseCon2023 CODECO video (ECL). - Zenodo community²⁴ (FOR, INO, UGOE). - YouTube (FOR)²⁵. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Website: 5295 views corresponding to 3256 visitors. - Zenodo: 3372 views and 2835 downloads across all documents; 817 views and 735 downloads with focus on the deliverables related with OSS. - YouTube: 104 total views in the CODECO exclusive channel.
Press releases	All	Dissemination about the overall project development, results, and events.	4 per year (multiple partners) reaching to over 500 end-users.	All	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Eclipse newsletter 2023. - FOR online press releases. - Social network activities with focus on OSS. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Eclipse newsletter: over 250000 subscribers. - FOR press releases: over 200 views. - Social networks: 536 followers in LinkedIn; 134 in X (former Twitter) .
Industrial Event	DEV, ICT, AR	1 Inception event, industrial workshop (M12) Organised by FOR having as main target industrial stakeholders and aiming at igniting interest in further exploring the use-cases in multiple fields of IoT/Edge.	>50 participants	All	Preparation of demonstrations, code, and presentations/videos for the HIPEAC industrial workshop on 18.01.2023.	1 st Industrial Workshop: 62 attendees including students, researchers and SMEs.
Representation in events	ICT, AR, SDO, EUS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Disseminate CODECO results in different venues, industrial and scientific. - Promotion of active participation and discussions on exploitation aspects and community-building. 	>50 events	All	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EclipseCon (ECL), Ludwigsburg, Germany, 16th October 2023. - Eclipse SAAM on Cloud to Edge Continuum (ECL), 16th October 2023. - 6G CONASENSE workshop (FOR), co-located with IEEE WPMC2023, Orlando, USA, 29th Nov 2023. - MobiArch 2023 (UGOE, TID), Madrid, Spain, Oct 6th, 2023. - EUCEI concertation meeting (FOR), Brussels, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -EclipseCon: over 200participants. - 6G CONASENSE: 40 participants. - MobiArch 2023: 30 participants. - EUCEI Concertation meeting: >100 participants. - WF-IoT 2023: 70 participants. - Nexus Forum 2023: >100 participants. - AI-SPRINT final event: 70 participants. - Embedded World 2024: >100 participants.

²⁴ <https://zenodo.org/communities/he-codeco>²⁵ First video added in M11 (November 2023).

Dissemination Activity	Targets	Aim	KPIs (D21)	Lead/ Contributors	Open-source contributions, year 1 and year 2	Impact
					Belgium, 10 th to 11 th May 2023. - WF-IoT 2023 (FOR), Aveiro, Portugal, 23 rd October 2023. - Nexus Forum 2023 (i2CAT), Brussels, Belgium, 5 th to 6 th October 2023. - AI-SPRINT final event (FOR), online, 11 th October 2023. - Embedded World 2024 (ECL), Nuremberg, Germany, 9 th to 11 th April 2024. - Dev.Conf.CZ (RHT), Brno, Czechia, 13 th to 15 th June 2024. - AAAI2023 (UGOE), Washington DC, USA, 14 th to 15 th February 2023, - EUCNC CONASENSE 2024 (FOR), Antwerpen, Belgium, 3 rd June 2024. - IEEE ISCC ECO 2024 (ATH), Paris, France, 26 th June 2024,	- DevConf.CZ: >100 participants. - AAAI2023: >20 participants. - EUCNC CONASENSE 2024: 60 participants. - IEEE ISCC ECO 2024: 20 participants.
Advanced training ²⁶	ICT, AR, DEV, SDO	- Transfer results and address potential gaps derived from interaction with the scientific community. - Specific events and participation in community events, e.g., summer schools, Webinars, workshops.	>20 organized training events with at least 50 participants	INTRA, ECL	3 trainings provided by ECL: Open-source ecosystem; Open-source licensing and compliance; Open collaboration, open development.	All partners involved, average of 40 persons in each workshop.
CODECO GitLab Repository	DEV, ICT, AR	Re-use of OSS code. Community engagement.	N/A	ECL, All	- Early release of OSS code as defined in D11, M10. CODECO Open-source Toolkit, and in D12. - Continuous development, open and transparent collaboration.	52 developers

²⁶ Advanced training activities in CODECO are to be started in year 3 of the project, T7.4. However, partner Eclipse has started advanced training internally for the consortium, to bootstrap an understanding of building results towards OSS.

Additionally, the next subsections provide more information, including the measure of impact, for some of those actions. For each activity, a brief description and an assessment of its impact for the CODECO community-building are provided.

5.3 Media Dissemination and Press Releases

Having in mind the focus of OSS community-building, several efforts have been done, as described in Table 4:

- Across the CODECO LinkedIn space, partner INO has been driving several dissemination activities, covering OSS results of the project, such as software release, among others. The CODECO LinkedIn has a total of 1706 page views with 536-page visitors.
- The Website has reached 3256 visitors corresponding to a total of 5295 views.
- The CODECO Zenodo community has reached a total of 3372 views and 2835 downloads, where 817 views and 735 downloads correspond to deliverables associated with the CODECO OSS components and architecture (deliverables D8, D9, D10, D11, D12).
- Different press releases have reached over two hundred views.
- CODECO's exclusive YouTube Channel, with 12 videos having been uploaded to it, totalling 104 views and 6 subscribers.

5.3.1 OSS Oriented Events

Key events have been held during the second year of project life, 2024, oriented to the DEV, AR, and ICT stakeholder groups:

- **OCX 2024**, organised by ECL, in Mainz, Germany, 22nd – 24th October 2024. Targets were DEV, AR, and ICT. It replaces the previous EclipseCon. CODECO participated on the *Research@Eclipse* booth, with the purpose of community engagement.
- **EUCNC CONASENSE 2024²⁷**, organised by EUCNC in Antwerp, Belgium, 3rd June 2024. Targets were AR and ICT. The workshop focused on the continuous alignment of CODECO as a representative of 6G Cloud-Edge-IOT architecture and interaction with other EU projects.
- **Embedded World 2024²⁸**, organised by ECL, in Nuremberg, Germany, 9th - 11th April 2024, depicted in Figure 13. Targets were DEV and ICT. With more than 32,000 attendees at the event, CODECO was present at a booth and had the opportunity to do networking with other stakeholders.
- **DevConf2024**, organised by RHT, in Brno, Czech Republic, 13th – 15th June 2024. Targets were DEV, AR, and ICT. Dean Kelly and Alka Nixon had the opportunity to give a talk: *Introduction of CODECO, overview, architecture, Red Hat work on CODECO*. More than 1,100 attendees registered at the event, making it an opportunity to meet the developer community.
- **European Big Data Value Forum 2024²⁹**, organised by BDVA, in Budapest, Hungary, 2nd – 4th October. Targets were AR, GOV, and ICT. The event focused on advance policy actions and industrial and research activities in the areas of Data and AI. CODECO was represented in one of the sessions, titled "*AI and data over computing continuum*", where the latest developments in the projects were highlighted.

²⁷ <https://www.eucnc.eu/programme/workshops/workshop-11/>

²⁸ <https://www.embedded-world.de/en>

²⁹ <https://european-big-data-value-forum.eu/>

- **AIOTI Days 2024³⁰**, organised by the Alliance for IoT and Edge Computing Innovation (AIOTI), in Brussels, Belgium, 24th – 26th September 2024. Targets were DEV, AR, and ICT. Rute C. Sofia presented CODECO’s architecture and its experimental framework. The workshop focused on the exploration of how the continuum and digital twins meet virtual worlds in industrial space, creating a physical-digital virtual continuum.
- **Red Hat Tech Talk**, organised by RHT, in Cork, Ireland, 14th February 2024. Targets were DEV, AR, and ICT. Dean Kelly and Alka Nixon had a talk in front of 60 attendees: *Introduction to CODECO, overview*. Figure 14 shows a capture of the talk.

Figure 13. CODECO at Embedded World 2024, in Nuremberg.

³⁰ <https://aioti.eu/aioti-days-2024/>

Figure 14. Red Hat team presenting CODECO at Tech talk, Ireland.

Out of the different events, we highlight OCX 2024 due to the focus and broader reach.

In OCX 2024, CODECO attended the Open Community Experience (OCX). The event lasted 4 days, with a variety of collocated events addressing innovative CODECO-related topics, such as embedded IoT and edge, automotive and mobility and supply chain security, among others.

Impact Assessment: OCX, formerly EclipseCon, is the Eclipse Foundation's flagship conference and meeting point for developers, architects, researchers and open-source business leaders to learn about Eclipse technologies, share experiences and best practices in open-source software development, and more. More than 430 attendees had the opportunity to gain experience about CODECO at the Research Booth, shown in Figure 15, along with the CODECO poster displayed at the poster session, and the flyers and stickers produced and distributed, resulting in good acceptance among the developer community.

Figure 15. CODECO present at OCX 2024.

5.3.2 Engagement in OSS Communities

In addition to the development of specific events, and participation in external events, CODECO has been involved in different OSS communities, contributing to the creation of OSS paths in Europe. This section summarizes the contributions held so far.

5.3.2.1 EUCloudEdgeIoT Engagement

The EUCloudEdgeIoT.eu initiative aims to realise a pathway for the understanding and development of the Cloud, Edge and IoT continuum by promoting cooperation between a wide range of research projects, developers and suppliers, business users and potential adopters of this new technological paradigm. The initiative manages six Task Forces (TFs): TF1 Strategic Liaisons, TF2 Open-source Engagement, TF3 Architecture, TF4 Ecosystem Engagement, TF5 Market and Sectors, TF6 Communications.

Different partners in CODECO are engaging across all TFs. Specifically, FOR is involved in TF1, TF3, and TF6. ECL leads TF2, therefore providing input from CODECO as well. ATOS leads TF3. Moreover, INO is expected to engage in TF1, TF4, and TF6 in the context of the CODECO Innovation and Research Community Engagement Programme (IRCEP), which started in 2024. Key contributions of CODECO in the context of EUCloudEdgeIoT are expected

to result from its framework (architecture and taxonomy); OSS guidelines (TF2); use-case aspects towards SDOs (TF1).

Impact Assessment: For CODECO, the EUCloudEdgeIoT.eu initiative is an excellent opportunity to interact and align with the cluster of similar European projects and share ongoing work and results within relevant working groups. What is also relevant is the definition of taxonomy and the architectural view for the Edge-Cloud continuum where CODECO is involved. For the period being reported, in addition to contributions to TF3 (taxonomy, architecture), CODECO has engaged in TF1 in the context of developed white papers, and concerning its use-cases, and novelty concerning Edge/IoT applications.

5.3.2.2 HiPEAC

The HiPEAC initiative addresses topics across the compute continuum from Edge to Cloud, HiPEAC is a network of around 2,000 world-class computing systems researchers, industry representatives, and students, i.e. the AR, ICT and DEV stakeholder of CODECO. CODECO organised an industrial workshop in HiPEAC 2024, has prepared another workshop for the HiPEAC 2025 Conference³¹ and is going to regularly engage with the initiative across different activities, e.g., summer schools via the CODECO IRCEP programme (T7.2, started in April 2024, M16 of CODECO).

CODECO had a first contact with the HiPEAC community at the project's first industrial workshop³², inception event, which took place on 18.01.2024, co-located with HiPEAC 2024, in Munich. The HiPEAC conference run over three days and attracted over 1000 participants. The event targeted AR, ICT, and the DEV community as well. It provided demonstrations based on the CODECO Toolkit open-source code; presentations and videos about the CODECO use-cases were shown. It also counted with a panel involving two other projects of the cognitive continuum, COGNIFOG³³, and COGNIT³⁴. Figure 16 shows one of the presentations at the workshop, about the NetMA component.

The second HiPEAC community initiative will take place on January 22nd, 2025, with a Machine Learning for Edge-Cloud Systems³⁵ (ML4ECS) workshop where CODECO will have a dedicated session.

Impact Assessment: The first event attracted over 20 attendees, among the 44 registered participants. The aim was to ignite interest across HiPEAC, which will be continued with other related activities, targeting the community, such as the workshop at HiPEAC 2025, participation in summer schools, etc.

³¹ <https://www.hipeac.net/2025/barcelona/#/>

³² <https://he-codeco.eu/codeco-industrial-workshop/>

³³ <https://cognifog.eu/>

³⁴ <https://cognit.sovereignedge.eu/>

³⁵ <https://www.hipeac.net/2025/barcelona/#/program/sessions/8194/>

Figure 16. First CODECO inception workshop, collocated with HIPEAC 2024 conference.

5.3.2.3 AIOTI

AIOTI³⁶ focuses on leading, promoting, bridging, and supporting collaboration in IoT and Edge Computing and other converging technologies research and innovation, standardisation, and ecosystem building, providing IoT and Edge Computing deployment for European businesses creating benefits for European society.

Several partners of CODECO, such as FOR, ICOM, and I2CAT, are involved across different Working Groups (WGs) of AIOTI. In regard to the targets of OSS, groups that the consortium believes are relevant concern the Horizontal AIOTI groups, *Research and Innovation* and *Standardisation*, and the vertical groups, *Manufacturing*, *Energy*, *Mobility*.

The key aspects involving CODECO partners concern the development of a common vision towards IoT-Cloud-Edge, addressing relevant challenges over the next decades (Research and Innovation), and the application of CODECO in its use-cases (Standardisation, specific vertical groups) and other vertical groups.

Impact Assessment: The key aspect under work in AIOTI relates with CODECO awareness and the re-use of CODECO. Currently, the CODECO OSS is being considered across novel project proposals under development with collaboration of AIOTI, and with AIOTI partners.

³⁶ <https://aioti.eu/>

6 OSS Community-building Planned Activities

Several OSS community-building activities are already being planned, being the proposed timeline until the end of the project illustrated in

Figure 17. This figure provides a broad grained perspective, where only the main events are highlighted. However, specific activities led by different partners which are already under development are listed in Table 5. These activities are therefore a complement to the plan and contributions already detailed in Table 3, and which will be revised for the next version of this deliverable, D26, due in M36 (December 2025) of CODECO.

As exploitation starts to gain importance for the next and last year of life of CODECO (led from tasks T7.3 and T7.4), the IP work, which has been developed during the last twelve months, is leaving its place to open-source and community-building related exploitation activities. The community around a project starts from the consortium itself, and therefore during the next twelve months the CODECO partners will start thinking of committing to maintain the CODECO code in the long term, creating a new project or collaborating with existing open-source ones and contributing back to the open-source community.

One of the community-building activities planned for the next year is the CODECO hackathon. Originally drafted to take place in Dublin in November 2024, it has been rescheduled to happen in Madrid in July 2025, during the IETF-123 meeting³⁷. It will allow for the CODECO Toolkit to be more mature and in more advanced state, increasing the potential of the hackathon results and developments.

An additional aspect to highlight is that CODECO counts with a specific community engagement programme under WP7, the *CODECO Innovation and Research Community Engagement Programme (IRCEP)*, led by partner INO and started in April 2024, M16 of the project. IRCEP counts with a number of specific events dedicated to community-building and community engagement. IRCEP was presented to the target stakeholders by first time in the CODECO inception event in HiPEAC 2024, January 2024. No opportunities were made available under IRCEP in 2024 as the events where CODECO participated did not fully align with this initiative's objectives. For 2025, however, initiatives are already in place where IRCEP will be deployed, starting in January 2025 with HiPEAC 2025 and then, specifically tailored actions such as CODECO's Innovation Challenges and the CODECO Hackathon. Other initiatives are continuously monitored and analysed to see if they fit within IRCEP.

³⁷ <https://www.ietf.org/meeting/123/>

Figure 17. Main OSS community-building activities foreseen from M12 until M36.

Table 5. Initial OSS community-building activities foreseen for the third year of CODECO.

Activity	Targets	Aim	Expected	KPIs	Lead
CODECO Development event 2: Dagstuhl seminar "Edge-Cloud data-compute-network orchestration"	ICT, AR	Discuss challenges concerning orchestration aspects and concerning OSS deployment.	M36	>50 participants	UGOE
CODECO workshop: second industrial workshop	ICT, AR, DEV	The CODECO Open-source Toolkit will be part of the ML4ECS Industrial Workshop ³⁸ organized in the scope of HiPEAC2025 (January 2025).	M25	>50 participants	FOR, I2CAT, UPRC
HIPEAC 2025, January 2025	DEV, AR, ICT	Participation of CODECO in a booth at the HIPEAC conference, co-located with the Industrial workshop ML4ECS.	M25	>70 participants	ECL
Hackathon	DEV, AR, ICT	In the IRCEP CODECO programme, it is envisioned to have a Hackathon, planned in July 2025 co-located with IETF121 meeting, in Madrid.	M31	>50 participants	INO, ECL
RedHat research meetings (every month)	DEV, ICT	Organized once per month, RHT will carry input of CODECO	M25-M36	Participation in 1 event per month	RHT
DevConf.cz ³⁹ , June 2025	DEV, AR, ICT	Open-source conference, June 12 th -14 th 2025, proposal being planned	M30	>50 participants	RHT

³⁸ <https://ml4ecs.e-ce.uth.gr/>

³⁹ <https://www.devconf.info/cz/>

Activity	Targets	Aim	Expected	KPIs	Lead
CONASENSE 2025, June 2025	DEV, AR, ICT	Workshop to be co-located with a European conference, planned for June 2025. CODECO will have a section with demonstrations in the workshop	M30	>50 participants	FOR
Red Hat Summit, May 2025	DEV, AR, ICT	Annual Red Hat Conference, RHT plans to provide a talk about CODECO. May 19 th – 22 nd 2025.	M29	>50 participants	RHT
OSS events during the CODECO IRCEP	ICT, AR, DEV	Joint organization of events during the IRCEP programme, e.g., demo camps, etc.	M32	>20 participants	INO, ECL
ICCN workshop 2025, May 2025	ICT, AR	International Workshop on Intelligent Cloud Computing and Networking organized in conjunction with IEEE INFOCOM 2025, May 19 th , 2025. CODECO participating as steering committee, TPC member.	M29	>20 participants	UGOE
ACM MobiArch 2025	ICT, AR	Joint workshop with MobiCom 2025. CODECO participating as steering committee, TPC member. November 2025.	M35	>20 participants	UGOE
ACM MobiCom 2025	ICT, AR	CODECO participating as General Vice Chair. November 4 th – 8 th 2025.	M35	>50 participants	UGOE
Nacht des Wissens Göttingen (Night of Science) 2025	ICT, AR, EUS	Plans a demo for the public, especially school pupils. It is expected to have over 2500 visitors to this event. Jun 21 st , 2025	M30	>50 participants	UGOE

7 Summary and Next Steps

The first six months of Task 7.1, during year 1, were about setting up the open collaboration environment, basic training and creating first awareness of CODECO in the open-source communities. During the following twelve months, the focus has been put on the IP aspects of the code and repository, while gathering the first developers interested in the CODECO open-source Toolkit. As the project is entering its third year, the focus is shifting from the IP side of CODECO towards the exploitation of the Toolkit, without discarding the community which is being built around the code.

This initial phase allowed the consortium to, under the leadership of partner ECL, get acquainted with adequate OSS guidance; understand key aspects in regard to licensing; agree on a common OSS vision, and start preparing the next phase of OSS community engagement. The second period (M13-M24) corresponded to a community engagement ramp-up phase, once the project has reached its “maturity” phase: consolidation of the CODECO open-source components into a Toolkit; enhancement of the open-source repository through the implementation of open-source best practices; start activities to engage the future OSS community; attendance of events targeting different groups of stakeholders.

As next steps, the following aspects are the basis for the work to be developed in the next period, and to be reported in the next and last version of this deliverable, D26 (due M36):

- Continue performing the IP work and implementation of open-source best practices, keeping the CODECO Open-source Toolkit and the CODECO Research Labs repository as the basis for the community engagement.
- Continue working to “FREE” the CODECO community (Feed, Respect, Embrace and Engage the developer community).
- To regularly assess the state of the CODECO Open-source Toolkit in respect to the potential creation of new Eclipse projects or (upstream) integration with existing projects (e.g., RedHat ACM).
- To increase the impact and community engagement, via the CODECO IRCEP, and additional activities being taken in the project, such as the CODECO hackathon.

8 Appendix 1 – OSS Community-building Year 1

This section summarizes all the community building activities performed during the first twelve months of the CODECO project life, which have been extracted from the previous version of the deliverable D24, with special focus to the ones implemented between M7 and M12, not only because T7.1 had started, but also because the CODECO concept and toolkit had 'taken shape' and were mature enough to be disseminated. open-source perspective.

Similarly to Table 4 in Section 5, Table 6 shows the activities (during year 1), their impact and the contribution to them from the open-source perspective.

Table 6. Open-source community-building activities held until M12.

Dissemination Activity	Targets	Aim	KPIs (D21)	Lead/Contributors	Open-source contributions, year 1	Impact
Media dissemination	All	Dissemination of the overall project development via broad media, e.g., TV, podcasts, YouTube videos, public magazines, and journals.	1 per year	FOR, ECL, INO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Website (INO, FOR). - Involvement in EUCEI (open-source, ECL, FOR). - ECL Eclipse2023 CODECO video. - Zenodo community (FOR, INO, UGOE). - YouTube (FOR). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Website: 250 visitors, over 600 views. - Zenodo: 603 views across all documents; 313 with focus on the deliverables related with OSS. - YouTube: 70 views on the first video since mid-November 2023.
Press releases	All	Dissemination about the overall project development, results, and events	4 per year (multiple partners) reaching to over 500 end-users	All	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Eclipse newsletter 2023 - FOR online press releases - Social network activities with focus on OSS (INO) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Eclipse newsletter: over 250000 subscribers. - FOR press releases: over 200 views - Social networks: 399 followers in LinkedIn; 91 in Twitter
Industrial Event	DEV, ICT, AR	1 Inception event, industrial workshop (M12) Organised by FOR having as main target industrial stakeholders and aiming at igniting interest in further exploring the use-cases in multiple fields of IoT/Edge.	>50 participants	All	Preparation of demonstrations, code, and presentations/videos for the HiPEAC industrial workshop on 18.01.2023	To be provided after event (18.01.2023); currently 44 attendees from 32 institutions in 14 countries.

Dissemination Activity	Targets	Aim	KPIs (D21)	Lead/Contributors	Open-source contributions, year 1	Impact
Representation in events	ICT, AR, SDO, EUS	Disseminate CODECO results in different venues, industrial and scientific. Promotion of active participation and discussions on exploitation aspects and community-building.	>50 events	All	- EclipseCon, Ludwigsburg (Eclipse, dissemination), 16th October 2023 - Eclipse SAAM on Cloud to Edge Continuum (Eclipse, dissemination), 16th October 2023 - 6G CONASENSE workshop (co-located with IEEE WPMC2023, 29th Nov, Orlando, FL, USA, organized by fortiss) - MobiArch 2023 (UGOE, TID - Workshop Chairs), Madrid, Spain, Oct 6th, 2023.	- EclipseCon: over 200 participants. - 6G CONASENSE: 40 participants. - MobiArch 2023: 30 participants.
Advanced training	ICT, AR, DEV, SDO	Transfer results and address potential gaps derived from interaction with the scientific community. Specific events and participation in community events, e.g., summer schools, Webinars, workshops.	>20 organized training events with at least 50 participants	INTRA, ECL	3 trainings provided by ECL: Open-source ecosystem; Open-source licensing and compliance; Open collaboration, open development.	All partners involved, average of 40 persons in each workshop.
CODECO Eclipse GitLab	DEV, ICT, AR	Re-use of OSS code	-	ECL, All	Early release of OSS code as defined in D11, M10	35 followers

In the context of this category of activities, we highlight the Eclipse Newsletter due to its broad outreach. The CODECO project was part of the Eclipse Newsletter in July 2023. The article gave an overview of the CODECO concept and architecture, also with regard to the intended open-source results, and already referred to the CODECO GitLab repository. The title was "CODECO: Supporting the Edge-Cloud Continuum Via an Open, Cognitive, Decentralised Framework" and can be found on the Eclipse website⁴⁰.

Figure 18 shows the first part of the article.

⁴⁰

<https://newsroom.eclipse.org/eclipse-newsletter/2023/july/codeco-supporting-edge-cloud-continuum-open-cognitive-decentralized>

CODECO: Supporting the Edge-Cloud Continuum Via an Open, Cognitive, Decentralized Framework

Rute C. Sofia

Marco Jahn

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The current internet evolution, with an increasing focus on the intertwining of smart, mobile, decentralized IoT services, brings new challenges to the deployment of applications. Applications and their components need to be lightweight, highly portable, and mobile, to run anywhere and everywhere. Secondly, there is a need to handle large amounts of data often with very different features both in terms of computation (processing) and exchange (networking), including those with low latency demands. Third, it is important to guarantee a smooth data flow, to allow for a smooth and secure integration end-to-end, across edge-cloud environments. Fourthly, real-time decision-making on where to compute and to store data must be supported.

CODECO, a Horizon Europe project, is attempting to answer these needs (Figure 1), framing itself as an intelligent and decentralized edge-cloud orchestration framework that addresses the existing infrastructure by considering data, compute, and network resources.

Figure 1: The key principles and objectives of CODECO

CODECO develops an ecosystem consisting of open-source toolkits, large-scale experimentation, training tools and events, use-cases across four vertical domains (Smart Cities, Energy, Manufacturing, Smart Buildings) and multiple events integrated into a unique Innovation and Research Community Engagement Programme. The open source software, which is pluggable and interoperable with Kubernetes (K8s) will be made available to the community through the Eclipse Foundation.

A Novel Approach to Orchestration: Data-Compute-Network

CODECO will implement software toolkits suitable for smarter management of highly-distributed environments based on heterogeneous networks and by integrating mobile, resource-constrained devices. The CODECO components, illustrated in Figure 2, shall extend the management and orchestration of edge-cloud services with cognitive cross-layer adaptability and with features that allow for intelligent decisions regarding computational offloading and network adaptation while taking into consideration application and networking requirements, data security and sensitivity, as well as other context-specific aspects related to the data flow. CODECO plans to support both single cluster and federated cluster operations.

Figure 18. CODECO article in Eclipse Newsletter in July 2023.

Impact Assessment: The Eclipse Newsletter reaches more than 250.000 subscribers from the wider Eclipse ecosystem. The CODECO article was meant to be the first activity to drop the name “CODECO” and create awareness of the project in the open-source community.

Three other main events were held in 2023, oriented to the DEV, AR, and ICT stakeholder groups:

- **ACM Mobiarch 2023**⁴¹, having as chairs Tingting Yuan (UGOE) and Luis Contreras Murillo (TID), Madrid, Spain, Oct 6th, 2023. Targets were AR, ICT, and DEV. The workshop counted with a panel session organized by CODECO, dedicated to the architectural design, and disseminating the CODECO Eclipse GitLab. It counted with twenty participants.
- **EclipseCon 2023**, organized by Marco Jahn and David Remon, ECL, in Ludwigsburg, 16th-19th October 2023. CODECO participated on the research projects, with the purpose of community engagement. Targets were DEV, AR, and ICT.

⁴¹ <https://mobiarch2023.github.io/>

- **6G CONASENSE 2023⁴²**, co-located with IEEE WPMC2023, having as chair Rute C. Sofia (FOR), November 21st, 2023. Targets were AR and ICT. The workshop focused on 6G aspects, and one of the proposed topics was flexible Edge-Cloud continuum. It counted with fifty participants.

Out of the different events, we highlight EclipseCon 2023 due to the focus and broader reach.

In EclipseCon 2023, CODECO had the opportunity to meet the development community: more than 460 developers, architects, researchers, and managers attended the event. This event lasted a week, starting with a community day on Monday and ending on Thursday after three more days of conference. Figure 19 shows the interaction with the visitors at the booth.

Figure 19. CODECO poster and CODECO team during EclipseCon 2023.

Finally, in addition to the development of specific events and participation in external events, CODECO has been involved in different OSS communities, contributing to the creation of OSS paths in Europe, where the EUCloudEdgeIoT initiative can be highlighted. CODECO engaged in the first EUCloudEdgeIoT concertation meeting⁴³ both on the project pitching session and also having been invited to the panel “Resource orchestration and adaptation in the continuum.” There were around 100 attendees in this session (rf. to Figure 20 for a view on the event).

⁴² <https://www.conasense.org/conasense-2023/>

⁴³ <https://eucloudedgeiot.eu/concentration-and-consultation-meeting-on-computing-continuum-uniting-the-european-ict-community-for-a-digital-future/>, May 10th-11th 2023, Brussels.

Figure 20. First EUCloudEdgeIoT concertation meeting.

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